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The potential of machine learning algorithms for mapping microplastic concentrations in the ocean

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Abstract

Microplastic particles (plastic particles less than 5mm in size) floating at the ocean surface are a serious pollution problem in marine environment and can harm marine life and enter the food chain. Knowing the quantity and spatial distribution of microplastics is therefore necessary to assess the risk this pollutant poses to the environment. To date, the modelling of their distribution is mostly based on physical models capable of simulating particle transport by following ocean currents and parameterising other source and sink processes. In this thesis, we test the use of a completely data-driven approach to study the same pollution problem. Specifically, we assess different machine learning methods already used for mapping biological variables, to associate a microplastic dataset with some selected environmental and geospatial predictor variables in order to extrapolate microplastic concentrations in the oceans in space and time. We predict global surface microplastic concentrations at a monthly and 1° resolution running ensembles of 5 different statistical models of varying complexities and 25 different predictor sets. We found highest microplastic concentrations in the 5 subtropical gyres, the Mediterranean and the Red Sea and lowest concentrations in equatorial and upwelling regions. The global mean microplastic concentrations are in the order of several tens of thousands items/ km^2 resulting in tens of trillions of particles floating on the surface of the ocean. The main environmental drivers include physical/biogeochemical, transport and atmospheric variables and we found variables indicator of water masses such as sea surface temperature and salinity to be remarkably important. Uncertainties coming from the model and predictor choice are associated with a scarcity of observations in the outer predictor ranges, resulting in the highest uncertainty in polar regions. Random Forest (RF) and Gradient Boosting Machine (GBM), as well as the ensemble mean of all members are consistently more accurate than using two simple null models and are able to reproduce the large-scale latitudinal pattern found using physical models. We conclude that, as a first investigation, this data-driven approach has the potential of mapping microplastic concentrations in the ocean and further developments of this approach are desirable.

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*“ There is nothing like looking, if you want to find something.
You certainly usually find something, if you look,
but it is not always quite the something you were after.”*

- J.R.R. Tolkien, The Hobbit

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 From wonder to troubles

In our daily lives, it is impossible not to come into contact with plastic. No matter where you are or what you are doing, look around and you will find plastic. When chemist Leo Baekeland synthesised the first plastic resin called Bakelite in 1907 (Chalmin, 2019), he could not have imagined that it would become a global pollution problem within a century (Hale et al., 2020). The new material had ideal properties for use in several applications: it does not burn, boil or melt, is not dissolved by solvents and acts as an electrical insulator (Chalmin, 2019). Thanks to these multipurpose qualities, different scientists started to produce new synthetic materials such as PVC in 1912, cellophane in the following year, polyethylene in 1933 and polystyrene in 1944 (Chalmin, 2019). Initially, the major applications of this material were military but since the 1950s it entered everyday use, taking advantage of the change from reusable material to disposable contents (Geyer et al., 2017). From there on, the global plastic production by the major oil groups has grown exponentially (Chalmin, 2019), so much so that in 1976 the American Chemistry Council named it the most widely used material in the world (Moore and Phillips, 2012).

Today, the global plastic production amounts to approximately 350 million tonnes per year with an average annual growth rate of 8.5% since 1950 (Chalmin, 2019). To give an idea of the fast growth, plastic production in 2012 was 620% higher than in 1975 (Jambeck et al., 2015). Soon, from the wonder of this extraordinary material, the first problems emerged. Besides the uncontrolled production growth, the polluting potential of this material arises from its non-biodegradability since only controlled thermo-chemical processes are able to destroy plastic waste (Geyer et al., 2017). As a result, the generation of plastic waste began to become a pressing problem for municipalities. In 1960, plastic accounted for less than 1% of the total waste, while in 2005 it accounted for more than 10%.

Given the high production and the difficulty of disposal, the dispersion of plastic waste into the environment was inevitable. Nowadays, plastic has been found in all environmental compartments: in water, soils, air and biological systems (Hale et al., 2020) and even in remote areas such as in Arctic sea ice (Geilfus et al., 2019) and on the sea floor (Schluning et al., 2013). Plastic can thus be considered as *“one of the most pervasive and permanent pollutants, particularly in marine ecosystems”* (Van Sebille et al., 2020, p.2).

But how do we know that plastic is a problem in the marine environment? The first evidence of plastics found in the oceans dates back to 1972 on the Sargasso Sea surface (Carpenter and Smith, 1972) and since then the issue has gained more and more attention (see e.g. Lebreton et al., 2017; Jambeck et al., 2015). One event of particular importance was the discovery in 1997 by navigator and oceanographer Charles Moore of a huge floating rubbish patch called the Great Pacific Garbage Patch located in the North Pacific (Moore and Phillips, 2012). Captain Moore’s discovery had initially led people to think of a floating plastic island on which they could walk. The media contributed to spread the problem to the public, talking about a mass of waste twice

the size of Texas (Hale et al., 2020). However, it was the captain himself, following one of his expeditions in the ocean, who said that a better description of the Garbage Patch is a “*plastic soup*” (Moore and Phillips, 2012, p.9), meaning areas of very high concentration but not capable of forming such a continuous layer of plastic. The term has now entered common parlance when talking about plastic pollution in the oceans. Nowadays, the problem of plastic pollution is known both in the media and in the scientific community particularly with regard to the pollution in the oceans (Cole et al., 2011).

1.2 Sources and sinks

Studies estimate that between 4.8 and 12.7 million tons of plastic entered the oceans in 2010 (Jambeck et al., 2015), while 18.7 million tons entered the oceans in 2015 (Lang, 2018). Where does all this plastic come from?

Plastic can enter the marine environment through the direct human release: either through land-based sources or through sea-based sources. The land-based sources are determined by the size of the population and the quality of the waste management systems and counts China, Indonesia and Philippines as the main plastic emitters (Jambeck et al., 2015). The land-based sources of plastic comprise losses from landfills, burning of plastic, vehicle tire wear, paint and coatings, textile washing and wastewater treatment (Hale et al., 2020). Particularly in low-income countries, about half of the plastic is not collected and is lost to the environment and even a considerable proportion of the collected plastic ends up in open landfills that gradually release it into the environment (Lang, 2018).

Sea-based sources include fishing and aquaculture activities, disposal from vessels and storm-related debris (Hale et al., 2020). Abandoned fishing nets represent an important part of this marine litter and in addition to the release of plastic, they pose a major entanglement risk to marine fauna (Høiberg et al., 2022). Lebreton et al. (2018) found that 46% of the large marine debris in the Great Pacific Garbage Patch was composed by fishing nets. Overall, land-based sources are thought to contribute more than sea-based sources (Mellink et al., 2022), although the latter cannot be overlooked (Van Sebille et al., 2020). Estimates suggest that the ratio is 80 to 20 (Jambeck et al., 2015).

Another source of plastic in the ocean, although poorly studied, is the atmosphere. Given the enormous interface surface between air and seawater, the atmospheric deposition is likely to be considerably high (Hale et al., 2020). This source of plastic is particularly relevant in remote areas, where deposition rates are similar to those in densely urbanised areas (Allen et al., 2019).

After the direct human release, wetlands, lakes and rivers play an important role in the dispersion and transport of plastic to the oceans (Hale et al., 2020). Numerous physical models parameterised the transport of plastic in rivers, but due to the scarcity of observations and the choice of parameters, the uncertainty regarding the export of plastic from rivers to oceans is still poorly constrained (Roebroek et al., 2022). A recent study by Meijer et al. (2021) was the first to include spatially explicit modelling of the transport from rivers to oceans and calculated that 1000 rivers account for 80% of the global riverine plastic export to the ocean for an annual total plastic load between 0.8 to 2.7 million tons. This illustrates the uneven contribution between the various rivers, since a few small rivers in particularly urbanised regions are among the largest contributors to plastic pollution (Meijer et al., 2021). Moreover, this study calculated that less than 2% of the land-based plastic produced close to rivers is emitted to oceans, highlighting that most of the plastic remain trapped in terrestrial environments. However, these models are not able to simulate the routes of plastic between the terrestrial compartments and only a recent study by Mellink et al. (2022) developed a new tool to simulate the pathways and spatiotemporal distribution of plastic within the river basin.

Once plastics have entered the oceans, many aspects that determine their fate are still unknown. This is primarily due to the fact that very little is known about the transformation of plastics in seawater (Van Sebille et al., 2015). In the ocean, plastics undergo a series of physical, chemical and

biological transformations that cause them to fragment into smaller and smaller polymers, thus affecting their buoyancy and transport (Hale et al., 2020). The fragmentation into smaller pieces, also called secondary microplastics (Cole et al., 2011), results after a combination of UV radiation, chemical degradation, wave mechanics and grazing by marine life (Van Sebille et al., 2015). Fragments smaller than 5mm are usually referred in the literature as microplastics (Van Sebille et al., 2015) and are the focus of this thesis. A schematic of the sources and sinks of microplastics in the marine environment is shown in Figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1: Simplified schematic of sources and sinks of microplastics in the global ocean. Inputs of microplastics are shown in red, while processes that control their distribution and export from the surface are in green. Image taken from Hale et al. (2020)

The size reduction combined with other processes is then able to change the buoyancy of the particles contributing to the sinking of the microplastics to the deep ocean. Sinking processes include the entrainment in marine snow, incorporation into fecal pellets, microplastic pump by giant larvaceans, aggregation with inorganic particles and biofouling (Van Sebille et al., 2020). The latter describes the algal attachment on an object's surface, causing the increase of its density and it is recognized as one of the most important sinks of surface microplastics (Lobelle et al., 2021). Biofouling can be parameterized in physical models and has been shown to influence the sinking timescales of microplastics (Lobelle et al., 2021). Since the process depends on the biota activity, the accumulation of microplastic in subtropical gyres is not only favoured by physical processes but also by the low algal concentrations in these oligotrophic zones (Lobelle et al., 2021). Overall, these processes highlight the importance of marine biota in moving the surface plastic to the depth (Van Sebille et al., 2020).

Another important sinking process is the trapping of microplastic particles in coastal zones also named beaching. Coastlines receive plastic litter both from terrestrial and marine sources (Cole et al., 2011) and microplastics have been consistently found in sediments in estuarine environments (Thompson et al., 2004) and in productive coastal upwelling regions (Doyle et al., 2011). The transport of microplastics along shorelines is different from the transport in the open ocean (Van Sebille et al., 2020) and it is influenced by the occurrence of multiple processes such as resuspension by waves and tides and onshore fragmentation into smaller pieces (Critchell et al., 2015). For this reason, coastal areas likely accumulate considerable amount of plastic (Lebreton et al., 2019). A modelling study by (Onink et al., 2021) found that at least 77% of the positively buoyant plastic released from land is either beached or floats in coastal waters.

The importance of the different processes that influence the vertical transport of microplastics is generally unclear and the removal processes rates essentially unknown (Van Sebille et al., 2020), meaning that many open questions remain regarding the movement and sinking of microplastic

particles in the ocean (Lobelle et al., 2021). These knowledge gaps about the sinks ultimately limit our ability to understand the ocean plastic budget and how much plastic resides in the different ocean reservoirs (Lobelle et al., 2021) as we will see in the next section.

1.3 Where are microplastics and why do we care

Besides the Great Pacific Garbage Patch discovered by Charles Moore, it is nowadays known that four other rubbish accumulation zones exist in the oceans due to the effect of ocean currents: the North Atlantic Garbage Patch, the South Atlantic Garbage Patch, the South Pacific Garbage Patch and the Indian Ocean Garbage Patch (Filho et al., 2021). These areas correspond to the subtropical gyres. The existence of these patches is supported from both observations (Law et al., 2010; Law et al., 2014) and theoretical and modelling knowledge (Lebreton et al., 2012; Maximenko et al., 2012).

The surface microplastic transport is governed by many different processes at different scales including Ekman currents, mesoscale eddies, Stokes drift, internal tides, wind forces, Langmuir circulation, vertical transport and mixing (Van Sebille et al., 2020). At the large-scale, the location of microplastic accumulation is largely determined by wind-driven Ekman currents, which due to their convergence in the subtropics lead to plastic accumulation in the subtropical gyres (Onink et al., 2019; Van Sebille et al., 2020). Geostrophic currents alone do not contribute to microplastic accumulation but they influence the shape of microplastic distribution, while Stokes drift do not contribute to the accumulation in subtropical gyres but increases the plastic transport to Arctic regions (Onink et al., 2019). This might be a possible explanation of the high microplastic concentrations observed in Arctic sea ice, several orders of magnitude higher than the concentrations in seawater (Geilfus et al., 2019).

At the mesoscale level, anticyclonic mesoscale eddies can trap, concentrate and transport microplastics and are associated with higher microplastic concentrations than cyclonic eddies (Brach et al., 2018). Moreover, jet-like features, also called striations play a role in the debris transport and can act as a possible exit route out of the subtropical zones (Maes et al., 2016; Van Sebille et al., 2020).

At the submesoscale level, debris accumulation have been found to occur at the density fronts and in cyclonic vortices, as opposed to what happens in mesoscale eddies (D’asaro et al., 2018). These processes are however typically not resolved in ocean models and in general the finer the scale, the more the details of these mechanisms remain unknown (Van Sebille et al., 2020).

Besides the uncertainty in modelling small-scale processes, the lack of knowledge about sources and sinks highlighted in the previous section means that the attempt to represent a global plastic budget is still incomplete (Van Sebille et al., 2015). One of the most important question marks in this area is the so-called “*missing plastic*” problem (Cressey, 2016). The problem arises from the fact that when comparing data on the amount of plastic entering the oceans with the observed amount within the upper ocean water column, it appears that a large portion of the plastic is missing. By comparing the two quantities, it is estimated that the former currently accounts for only 1% of the total rubbish entering the seawater (Van Sebille et al., 2015).

Several hypothesis might explain the missing plastic problem: these include the degradation into minute fragments below size detection limits, sinking processes, stranding and beaching of debris, ingestion by marine species, and incomplete observations (Cózar et al., 2014; Hale et al., 2020). This is on the one hand justified by the fact that a large amount of plastic tends to sink and therefore is not found in sea surface sampling and that larger floating objects are not quantitatively assessed in routine observations. On the other hand it shows that there is a lack of knowledge about removal processes and the amount of plastic residing in the reservoirs like in the middle and deep ocean or in the animal tissues (Van Sebille et al., 2015). Furthermore, the increase in plastic production in recent years has not been balanced by a significant increase in plastic concentrations in many parts of the ocean (Cressey, 2016).

This knowledge gap limits the ability to ascertain the impact of microplastics on wildlife and ecosys-

tems as we do not have enough information about the amount and distribution of microplastics once they enter ocean circulation. Another, partly related problem concerns field measurements. Collecting ocean data is expensive and difficult (Cressey, 2016). Many areas outside the gyres are undersampled (Van Sebille et al., 2015) as are the depths of the oceans (Cressey, 2016). Furthermore, any measurement technique captures only objects within a given size class (Van Sebille et al., 2020), while larger or smaller objects are simply disregarded. This is compounded by the difficulty of standardising data from multiple measurement campaigns due to different measurement techniques, units of measurement and ocean conditions during sample collection as wind and vertical mixing influence the amounts of microplastic collected (Kukulka et al., 2012).

Plastics have an impact on living organisms. It is widely known and documented that macroplastics (>5mm) and microplastics (<5mm) cause harm to marine animals (Wilcox et al., 2015). These include the entanglement of marine life, ghost fishing, ingestion of debris and even the transport of foreign species (Filho et al., 2021). The entanglement of large marine animals is largely reported and over 350 unique species including birds, turtles, fish and invertebrate have been observed to be entangled in large plastic debris (Kühn and van Franeker, 2020). Recently, the global impact of the entanglement of marine mammals, turtles and birds has been assessed providing a first insight into the impact of plastic entanglement on biodiversity (Høiberg et al., 2022).

In addition, the continual reduction in the size of plastic fragments reaching the micrometre and nanometre range creates a high risk of ingestion and makes the transport in the food chain extremely complicated (Cole et al., 2011). In a study by Kühn and van Franeker (2020), debris ingestion was recorded in 701 species and the highest number of macro- and microplastic items were found in seabirds. Macroplastic fragments are able to block or hinder the passage of food in the intestinal tract and microplastics can be absorbed in the tissue walls and cell membranes (Kühn and van Franeker, 2020). In addition, microplastics can induce a toxic response in the organisms inherent to the contaminants they leach (Cole et al., 2011). Given the large area to volume ratio, microplastics are prone to be contaminated by waterborne pollutants such as metals, endocrine disrupting chemicals and persistent organic pollutants (Hale et al., 2020). The transfer of microplastics in the food chain and the finding of microplastics in human tissue have also increased the concern for human health (Thompson et al., 2009). Further studies are still needed, but chemicals used in plastic manufacture have been correlated with reproductive abnormalities in human population (Swan, 2008).

Research about microplastic pollution has grown in recent years but many open questions still exist. The key point is that knowledge about the amount and distribution of microplastics in the oceans is fundamental to assess the risk that this type of pollution has on animals and humans. In this context, efforts to solve the problem have grown over the years. We can distinguish between 2 main categories of intervention. The first is crucial and consists of drastically reducing the amount of plastic produced and dispersed in the environment. Actions are being taken such as the ban on plastic bags or the increase in single-use bottle collection (Lang, 2018). Another effort are clean-up operations. Despite enormous engineering difficulties, some progress has been made. One example is the organisation *Ocean Cleanup* founded in 2013 with the ambitious goal of reducing the amount of floating plastic by 90% (see <https://theoceancleanup.com>, accessed 10.04.2023). Their work takes place in the oceans and rivers, and in addition to engineering, they are also involved in broader ocean plastic research.

Knowledge on the spatial distribution of microplastics on the ocean surface is a crucial objective in determining the risk this pollutant poses to the environment. Most studies carried out on this objective use physical models to establish the transport of plastic and its accumulation zones. Several studies have attempted to map the concentrations of microplastics in the global ocean (see e.g. Eriksen et al., 2014; Lebreton et al., 2012; Maximenko et al., 2012; Van Sebille et al., 2015) and in semi-enclosed seas (see e.g. Kaandorp et al., 2020; Pedrotti et al., 2022). These studies are based on a Lagrangian approach. This involves releasing virtual plastic particles into an ocean circulation model. The velocity field of the currents will then transport the particles and after a certain period it will be possible to highlight the main accumulation zones and map the global distribution of microplastics. The processes of particle release as well as sink can be parameterised

in various ways depending on the assumptions used and the degree of complexity of the model.

The studies using this approach indicate that the areas with the highest concentration of microplastics are the subtropical gyres with the North Pacific Ocean having the greatest mass of plastic as it is located between the large plastic emitters North America and Asia (Eriksen et al., 2014; Lebreton et al., 2012; Maximenko et al., 2012; Van Sebille et al., 2015). However, while different ocean basins have been compared in terms of relative differences in their plastic concentrations, we do not know the exact size of the patches (Filho et al., 2021). Moreover, we do not yet have a holistic picture of microplastics in low concentration regions outside the gyres. However, a study suggests that such areas can still contain around half of the total microplastic found in the oceans (Van Sebille et al., 2015). The major sources of uncertainty in these studies stem from the insufficient amount of data collected and from the parameterisation of processes such as coastal release and sinks (Cózar et al., 2014; Schmiz, 2021; Van Sebille et al., 2015).

This thesis aims to study the concentrations of microplastics at the ocean surface and its environmental drivers using a data-driven approach instead of the most used physical models. Using machine learning models to study marine plastic pollution is still in its early stages. To the best of our knowledge, these statistical methods have been used to predict pollution on beaches and optimise their cleaning (Granado et al., 2019; Kaandorp et al., 2022), assess the risk of plastic ingestion in the Mediterranean Sea (Fabri-Ruiz et al., 2023) and modelling the distribution of floating microfibers at the global scale (Lima et al., 2021).

To this end, we will assess the use of machine learning methods already used for mapping biological variables such as marine plankton (see Benedetti et al., 2021; Righetti et al., 2019), to associate a microplastic dataset assembled in Van Sebille et al. (2015) with some selected environmental and geospatial predictor variables to extrapolate microplastic concentrations in the oceans in space and time. It is the first time that a similar approach as developed specifically for the modelling of scarce and biased biological data sets is used on non-biological variables.

The central aim of the work is to assess the suitability of these statistical methods when modelling a non-biological variable. We will produce global monthly maps of microplastic concentrations by running 5 different statistical models of varying complexities and 25 different predictor sets. We will assess the resulting spatial pattern of accumulation and study the main environmental drivers of surface microplastic concentrations. We will validate the model performance by computing different goodness-of-fit metrics and by comparing our results against two null models and other results in the literature. Finally, we will quantify the uncertainty coming from the model and the predictor choice.

1.4 Research questions

Considering the aims of this thesis, we want to answer four main research questions:

- RQ1** What is the magnitude and spatial distribution of surface microplastic concentrations in the ocean? Do the results with machine learning algorithms agree with previous studies?
- RQ2** What are the main predictors that drive the distribution of surface microplastic concentrations in the ocean?
- RQ3** Are machine learning algorithms better than null models (averages of observations) in extrapolating microplastic concentrations? Which machine learning algorithm performs best?
- RQ4** How large is the uncertainty due to machine learning algorithm choice and predictor choice?

Chapter 2

Methods

Figure 2.1: Schematic modelling pipeline.

In order to estimate the concentrations of microplastics on the surface of the global ocean, we developed a multi-step modelling pipeline (see Figure 2.1). The first step is to collect and pre-process data for modelling. On the one hand we have the microplastic observations expressed in items/km² and subsequently standardized. On the other hand, the environmental climatologies. Afterwards, a univariate analysis aims to study the relationship between the environmental climatologies (i.e. predictors) and the target variable (i.e. microplastic observations) to select the most suitable predictors for modelling. The third step consists of running 5 different machine learning

models trained with the data described above that will each produce global maps of microplastic concentrations at a monthly 1° resolution. To study the uncertainty resulting from the choice of predictors, 25 different combinations of predictor sets are created. The different outputs will then be averaged on an annual basis and the best set (chosen set) and the average of all sets (ensemble mean) are analysed and compared against another independent modeled result and against two null models. In the last step, we validate the models and study the uncertainty arising from the model and predictor choice in order to establish the adequacy of machine learning algorithms in extrapolating the amount of microplastics and considering the availability of observations at the present time. A schematic flowchart of the work is presented in Figure 2.1.

2.1 Data

2.1.1 Overview microplastic dataset

Dataset characteristics

In this work we use an observational dataset of microplastics compiled in Van Sebille et al. (2015) and completed with additional observations by Schmitz (2021) in her master thesis. The dataset is an aggregation of 46 different sampling campaigns ranging from 1979 to 2019 and including all major ocean basins except the Arctic. It comprises a total of 13 159 records of microplastic concentrations expressed in either particles count per area (11 299 records), particles count per volume (1928), mass per area (73 records) or mass per volume (94 records).

The observations were taken using 3 main measurement methods, namely nets, bottles and pumps. Sampling with nets is the most common measurement technique, comprising 10 934 records using either Manta or Neuston net. Each study used different settings in terms of dimension of the net, trawling depth and net mesh size, whereas most studies did not report the maximum size of plastic debris and 1894 records do not have any depth information. The net mesh size used ranges from $100\ \mu\text{m}$ to $500\ \mu\text{m}$ with the majority being around $300\ \mu\text{m}$. Observations with a bottle comprises 1409 records, all of them by simply grabbing 1 L of seawater. Finally 347 records were taken using a pump. In addition, 469 records lack any information regarding the measurement method.

In this work we use only the observations measured as count per area so that all the observations taken with bottles or pumps are excluded. From all the observations with nets (10 934 records), 1860 of them were not expressed in count per area and are therefore excluded, resulting in 9074 available observations. To these we add 469 records with unknown measurement method, making a total of 9543 records.

Measurements expressed as counts per area are also standardized to consider different conditions during sampling (see Subsection 2.1.2 for details). These are slightly fewer than the raw observations, representing 8877 records with nets, plus 469 records with unknown method accounting for a total of 9346 observations.

Sampling effort in space and time

Another important consideration regarding the microplastic dataset is that the sampling effort has not been conducted homogeneously in space. This is clearly visible in Figure 2.2, which shows the number of records taken inside a grid cell of 1° by 1° during the period 1979-2019 and after the harmonisation described in Subsection 2.1.4.

The most represented ocean basins are the North Atlantic (1622 observations, 40% of the total) and North Pacific (1516 observations, 37.5% of the total) with a prevalence of observations towards the Western Atlantic and Eastern Pacific between the Equator and 45°N . The Arctic Ocean has no observations with only a couple of records just above 60°N located in the Labrador Sea and some more observations located slightly southern of 60°N in the Gulf of Alaska and Bering Sea. The Western Pacific is also relatively undersampled with a higher sampling effort only around the coast of Japan.

In the Northern Hemisphere, the Mediterranean Sea is the only sea represented with observations (11 observations, 0.3% of the total). These are mainly located towards the coasts of Italy and France. Any other European Sea, like the Baltic and Northern Sea lacks observations.

Moving towards the Southern Hemisphere, the number of records decreases. In particular, the Indian Ocean only has 84 observations (2% of the total) located in the Bay of Benguela, some more observations along the 30th parallel south and even more observations around the coasts of Australia. The South Atlantic (144 observations, 3.5% of the total) and South Pacific (410 observations, 10% of the total) are also relatively undersampled compared to the Northern Hemisphere. Moreover, the entire Southern Ocean is poorly represented with only 2 observations southern than 60°S in the Drake Passage.

Overall, 84% of the observations used for the modelling were collected in the Northern Hemisphere (3403 observations) and the remaining 16% in the Southern Hemisphere (646 observations).

Figure 2.2: Sampling effort (log. Number of records) per 1° by 1° grid cell.

Figure 2.3: Hovmöller diagram (latitude and month) of the sampling effort per 1° by 1° grid cell.

The sampling effort is also irregular in the time dimension. Figure 2.3 shows that the Northern Hemisphere Summer and early autumn months are quite underrepresented in the entire Southern Hemisphere with most of the observations in the Southern Hemisphere taken between December and May (84% of the total). On the other hand, the entire band between 30°N and 40°N has a good coverage between April and October but at higher latitude there are basically no observations in the winter months. The band between 20°S and 20°N has a prevalence of observations in the spring months, while the band between the Equator and 20°N has a prevalence between October and December.

Overall, April is the month with most records (553 observations), followed by December (461 observations), October (452 observations) and June (321 observations). On the other hand, September is the month with least records (132 observations) followed by August (146 observations) and January (182 observations).

These important data gaps, both in space and time, can represent a limitation of this work, since they can ultimately affect the model performance and largely limit the possibility of making accurate prediction of the target variable in certain regions. This issue will be considered during the validation stage.

High and low concentrations zones

A clear latitudinal pattern already emerges from the available observations of microplastics, especially for the North Atlantic and North Pacific where most of records originate from. Figure 2.4 shows the measured microplastic concentrations and the concentrations after the standardization process (see Subsection 2.1.2). Note that the grey dots in the raw observations correspond to an absence of microplastics (i.e. concentrations of 0 items/km²). The lack of these points in the standardized observations indicates that the standardization process tends to eliminate the absence of microplastic.

Looking at Figure 2.4, and focusing on the Northern Hemisphere, we can notice that the highest concentrations are located around 30°N both in the Pacific and Atlantic. This pattern emerges both in the raw and in the standardized observations with concentrations in these areas that can be four orders of magnitude higher than around the Equator.

In the Southern Hemisphere, although the number of observations is much smaller, the pattern is similar with a peak of high concentrations located at 30°S. However, the maximum peak is about an order of magnitude lower than the peak in the Northern Hemisphere.

This clear spatial pattern at the large-scale agrees with the results of modelling studies that use Lagrangian particle simulators. For example, Lebreton et al. (2012) and Maximenko et al. (2012), found that after decadal simulations, there is a clear formation of 5 accumulation zones in the subtropical latitudes. These accumulation zones, commonly named as garbage patches are formed by the circulation of the gyres with the North Pacific Garbage Patch being the largest one (Filho et al., 2021).

Besides observational and modelling evidences there is also theoretical knowledge that suggests that the subtropical gyres are accumulation areas. In fact, the oceanic large-scale circulation driven by surface winds, generate an Ekman drift which converges towards the five subtropical gyres and diverge in the subpolar gyres (Van Sebille et al., 2020). This transport mechanism is therefore responsible for the large-scale accumulation of plastic in the oceans, which our observational dataset confirms.

Other known regions of plastic accumulation are semienclosed seas with a surrounding high human density (Cózar et al., 2017). In our observational dataset, indeed the Mediterranean Sea seems to have high microplastic concentrations. Recently, also the Barents Sea has been proposed as another highly polluted region (Pogojeva et al., 2021), but unfortunately we do not have any observations there. Another highly polluted area based on observations seems to be the coasts of Japan which have a high population density. This is consistent with the results by Isobe et al. (2015) that found that concentrations in the Sea of Japan are 27 times higher than in the global oceans. Moreover,

the sea surrounding the coasts of Southeast Asia is also expected to be highly polluted given the high input coming from mismanaged plastic waste (Jambeck et al., 2015; Lang, 2018), even though we do not have enough observations in that region to assess this.

Figure 2.4: Maps of measured microplastics concentrations for the raw observations (top) and the standardized observations (bottom). The grey dots correspond to the location where no microplastics were measured (i.e. concentrations of 0 items/km²).

2.1.2 Microplastic data standardization

In this subsection, we summarize the standardization procedure that has been carried out by Van Sebille et al. (2015). The need for this procedure comes from the fact that microplastics were collected under different atmospheric and oceanic conditions and over a period of several decades, which make the entire microplastic dataset difficult to compare without an appropriate standardization. The additional variability coming from sampling year, wind speed, distance of the tow and others can influence the microplastic observations and undermine the representativeness of the samples. For example, Kukulka et al. (2012) demonstrated that due to wind-driven mixing, surface measurements can significantly underestimate plastic concentrations.

To eliminate the effect of these factors on the observations, Van Sebille et al. (2015) trained a Generalized Additive Model (GAM) with a spherical smooth term to find the relationship between sampling year, wind speed, trawl length and study ID on the target variable. The predictions of the best GAM were then used for deriving a standardized dataset. This is defined as if the samples had been collected without wind and in the reference year 2014. For additional details see Van Sebille et al. (2015).

Figure 2.5 shows a comparison between the raw and the standardized observations which is useful to determine the effect of the standardization procedure on the dataset. Two main features can be noticed: first, most of the standardized observations lie above the identity line, indicating that the standardization tends to increase the microplastic concentrations. As expected, the procedure balances out the fact that observations tend to be underestimated under the effect of wind. Another effect, as noted earlier, is that standardization eliminates any absence of plastic as can be seen by the vertical line of dots on the far left of the graph. This means that the standardized dataset contains no zero concentrations of microplastics. The minimum value in this case corresponds to 260 items/km².

Figure 2.5: Standardized microplastic concentrations against raw observations. The aligned dots to the left margin of the plot represent the absences that after the standardization have higher values.

2.1.3 Candidate predictors data

The choice of the entire pool of potentially explanatory variables (predictors) for microplastic concentrations is based on an extensive literature research. The number of studies found that apply a similar method as in this work is very limited, indicating that the use of machine learning to model microplastic concentrations is still in its early stages.

The most similar paper found is the one by Fabri-Ruiz et al. (2023). Overall, their methodology is very similar but it focuses only on the Mediterranean Sea and uses a different machine learning algorithm (Xgboost). Moreover, the study models the ratio of zooplankton to plastic to quantify the ingestion risk. The paper considers different physical, biogeochemical, lagrangian and eulerian explanatory variables and found that kinetic energy, turbulent kinetic energy and nitrates are the best predictors (Fabri-Ruiz et al., 2023). However, it must be considered that the modelling of a semi-enclosed basin can be very different than of entire ocean basins. The study in fact found that the Mediterranean has no stable accumulation zones due to the strong variability of currents contrary to what we observe in the open ocean.

The other most similar study at the global scale is the one by Lima et al. (2021). Here the main difference with this work is that it models only microfiber concentrations using GAMs. In addition, the used global microplastic dataset is smaller and was collected using bottle grab and not with nets. Using different physical, biogeochemical, atmospheric and transport variables, their results indicate that sea surface temperature, salinity, current velocity and wind speed are the best explanatory variables.

All the other studies were selected because they report a certain kind of relationship between the predictor and microplastics, mostly in terms of correlation in the observations, despite the different methodology. This provides evidence that these predictors are potentially good explanatory variables. The complete list of the literature assessed to define the candidate predictors is shown in Table A.2.

At the end of the literature review, the list contains 28 potentially good predictors, which we divided into 7 categories as visible in Table 2.1. The wind predictors in the atmospheric category comes from the *ERA5* reanalysis of *ECMWF* (Hersbach et al., 2020), while the wind direction was directly computed from the northward and eastward wind field using the *atan2* function in *Climate Data Operator* (Schulzeida, 2022).

Water depth was taken from *ETOPO1* of *NOAA* (Amante and Eakins, 2009). Chlorophyll concentrations comes from the *SeaWifs* product by *NASA's Ocean Colour Web* (NASA OB.DAAC, 2018).

The distance to closest coast, city and rivers were computed by Fabio Benedetti. The first, uses bathymetry data from *ETOPO1* (Amante and Eakins, 2009) and defines the coasts as cells having altitude larger than 5 m. The second uses the cities dataset from *opendatasoft* (<https://download.geonames.org/export/dump/>, accessed, 15.03.2022) and selects only the ones with a number of inhabitants above 100 000. The third uses the river dataset from GRDC (Fekete et al., 2002) and considers only the ones with elevation below 50 m, so that only rivers not too distant from the coasts are included.

The fishing hours dataset is a proxy of fishing effort and consequently of the main vessel routes which are thought to be important plastic emitters (Li et al., 2016). It was derived from the *Global Fishing Watch* dataset (Kroodsma et al., 2018) that makes use of satellite and neural network classifier to derive the time a given vessel remains in a grid cell at a daily resolution.

The dissolved inorganic carbon was taken from *OceanSODA-ETHZ* (Gregor and Gruber, 2021). Dissolved oxygen concentrations, nitrate concentrations and phosphate concentrations are from *World Ocean Atlas Project 2018 (WOA2018)* of *NOAA* (Garcia et al., 2019). The mixed layer depth comes from *Simple Ocean Data Assimilation (SODA)* ocean climate reanalysis (Carton et al., 2018).

Sea surface salinity is a *ESA* product from *CCI SMOS* mission (Olmedo et al., 2017). Sea surface temperature comes from the *NASA Optimum Interpolation SST V2* product (Huang et al., 2020).

In the transport category, the eastward geostrophic currents velocity, northward geostrophic currents and sea level anomaly are part of the altimeter products of *AVISO global delayed time L4* (AVISO, 2016) downloaded from the *E.U. Marine Copernicus Service Information CMEMS* platform (<https://marine.copernicus.eu>). The reference period to assess the sea level anomaly was 1993-2012.

The eddy kinetic energy was computed from the above fields by Fabio Benedetti using the formula in Qiu and Chen (2004). The currents direction, divergence, and relative vorticity were derived from the current fields using the *atan2*, *wv2dv* and *wv2vr* functions in *CDO* (Schulzeida, 2022).

Similarly, for the wind divergence we applied the *wv2dv* function using the eastward and northward wind fields as input. Where not already available, all predictor data were converted to Network Common Data Form (NetCDF). Additional information about the environmental datasets is listed in Table A.1.

Table 2.1: Pool of all predictors of microplastic concentrations in the ocean divided into the 7 categories. The variable nickname is the name we will use to refer to the predictor

Category	Candidate predictor	Variable nickname
Atmospheric	Eastward wind speed	wind_u10_era5
	Northward wind speed	wind_v10_era5
	Wind speed	windspeed_era5
	Wind direction	wind_direction
Bathymetry	Water depth	bathymetry_min_etopo1
Biological activity	Chlorophyll	chlorophyll_seawifs
Human activity	Distance to closest coast	dist2coast
	Distance to closest largest city	dist2cities
	Distance to closest largest river	dist2rivers
	Fishing hours	fishing_hours
Location	Latitude	degree_north
	Longitude	degree_east
Physical and biogeochemical	Dissolved inorganic carbon	dic_surf_osesthz
	Dissolved oxygen concentrations	oxygen
	Mixed layer depth	mld_soda
	Nitrate concentrations	nitrate
	Phosphate concentrations	phosphate
	Sea surface salinity	sss_cci_smos
Transport	Sea surface temperature	sst_oisstv2
	Currents direction	currents_direction
	Currents divergence	divergence
	Currents relative vorticity	relative_vorticity
	Eastward geostrophic currents velocity	ugos
	Eddy kinetic energy	EKE
	Geostrophic currents velocity	total_currents
	Northward geostrophic currents velocity	vgos
	Sea level anomaly	sla
Wind divergence	wind_divergence	

2.1.4 Data pre-processing

For all predictors, except for fishing_hours, we computed monthly climatologies and where necessary regridded the data to a 1° by 1° spatial resolution. For the fishing_hours, we considered only the data of 2016 and we aggregated them to a 1° by 1° grid and by month in order to obtain the total fishing hours per month per grid cell in the year 2016. Moreover, since the data contained a lot of absences (i.e. 0 fishing hours), we derived the zonal mean with a meridional resolution of 1°. For the entire analysis, we will use only this zonally averaged dataset.

At this point the standardized microplastic dataset and the gridded predictor datasets have been harmonized in terms of month, latitude, longitude and depth to match the World Ocean Atlas grid. The result of this procedure is a gridded dataset with a resolution of 1° by 1°, on the ocean surface and at a monthly resolution containing 4049 records for each predictor and the target variable.

Subsequently, the standardized microplastic concentrations were log-transformed since the observations range covered as much as 7 orders of magnitude. The same was done for chlorophyll_seawifs, EKE, fishing_hours, mld_soda, nitrate, phosphate and total_currents because these variables were right skewed and far from a normal distribution.

Finally we computed the zonal average with a latitudinal resolution of 1° for all candidate predictors except fishing_hours which is already a zonally averaged variable. At the end of the pre-processing stage, all the data are ready for the univariate analysis.

2.2 Univariate analysis

2.2.1 Predictor choice

The goal of the univariate analysis is to assess the most important predictors to keep for the modelling procedure and outline a first insight of the relationship between the target variable and the explanatory variables. This is done for two reasons. First, we want a semi-objective approach to rank the candidate predictors according to their ability to explain the variability in microplastic concentrations. In fact, the variables that show a strong relationship with the target variable are more desired to be included in a statistical model. The second reason is that we want to avoid both underfitting and overfitting in the machine learning algorithms, by selecting the simplest model that explain a relevant fraction of the variability (Merow et al., 2014).

Underfitting occurs when the model is not complex enough and/or the chosen predictors are not suitable, resulting in high bias and poor generalization (Hastie et al., 2016). On the opposite, overfitting occurs when there is too much model complexity and/or the ratio between number of predictor and number of observations is too high. Therefore, the number of observations is important and guiding in regard how many predictors can be used. When overfitting occurs, the model is not able to generalize well because it fits the noise resulting in a small prediction error in the training sample but not in the test sample (Hastie et al., 2016). The univariate analysis is used to skim the predictors that are not useful by keeping the predictor set as small as possible in order to avoid overfitting.

To select the final predictors from all the candidate predictors, we computed the variance explained by each predictor separately using univariate regression models. To this end we chose the two models with lower complexity from the models list described in Subsection 2.3.1.

We trained a Generalized Linear Model (GLM) with a Gaussian response function that includes a quadratic term and a Generalized Additive Model (GAM) with a cubic regression spline both performing a 5-fold cross validation. The deviance explained by each predictor and for each model was computed using Equation 2.1, where D_{null} is the null deviance and D_{res} the residual deviance:

$$D_{exp} = \frac{D_{null} - D_{res}}{D_{null}} \quad (2.1)$$

Then, we computed the mean deviance explained between GLM and GAM and we ranked all the candidate predictors according to this metric. The same procedure was applied but using the zonally averaged predictors at 1° latitudinal resolution to identify the large-scale effects of the predictors on the target variable. Finally, we chose only the predictors that met all 3 of the following criteria:

1. Mean deviance explained across GLM and GAM at the pixelwise level $>10\%$
2. Deviance explained by GAM at the pixelwise level $>10\%$
3. Mean deviance explained across GLM and GAM at the 1° zonal mean level $>10\%$

2.2.2 Predictor sets

Starting with the final predictors that fulfill all the 3 criteria listed above, we now want to find a semi-objective method that creates different sets composed by different combinations of final predictors. The goal is that one predictor within one set should not correlate too highly with any other predictor in the same set.

The need of creating multiple sets instead of one single model run comes from the fact that we do not have any a priori knowledge regarding the best number of predictors and in which combination to use them. By creating multiple realizations, we aim to test on one hand the effect of having different number of predictors on the model performance and on the other hand to evaluate the uncertainty coming from the predictor choice.

A common method for feature selection is hierarchical clustering. This method requires to specify a measure of dissimilarity between groups of observations and to compute it pairwise among the observations in the two groups (Hastie et al., 2016).

It is a common practice to avoid having too high multicollinearity within environmental predictor sets (Righetti et al., 2019). For this reason, we do not keep in one set two predictors that have a Spearman's Rank Correlation (ρ) greater than $|0.7|$. The chosen threshold is also used in other SDM studies as in Benedetti et al. (2021) and Righetti et al. (2019). In our case, only `sst_oisstv2` and `oxygen` are above this threshold (see Figure B.1), meaning that the two variables cannot belong to the same set.

As a result, our dissimilarity measure (DM) for the hierarchical clustering is based on the Spearman's Rank Correlation (ρ) and computed as:

$$DM = 1 - |\rho| \quad (2.2)$$

A simple method for feature selection already used in another study to predict coastal plastic pollution (see Kaandorp et al. (2022)) is a dendrogram: a tree structure where the height of each tree node corresponds to the DM between its two daughters (Hastie et al., 2016).

Subsequently, cutting the dendrogram at a certain height partitions the data into a certain number of clusters. The cut at a DM height of 1 classifies all the predictors in one single cluster, while at a DM of 0, each predictor belongs to its own cluster. Since we want to test the effect of having different number of predictors, we cut the dendrogram at 5 different heights to partition the predictors into k clusters with k ranging from 3 to 7. The clustering with $k=6$ is shown in Figure 2.6.

At this point, for each value of k we build 5 different combinations of predictors based on the average percentage deviance explained between the 3 criteria in the List 2.2.1. The procedure for defining the first set of predictors is as follows: for each value of k and each cluster, we choose the predictor in the cluster that has the highest average deviance explained. For the second set we choose the predictor in the cluster that has the second highest variance explained and so on until we build 5 sets for each of the 5 values of k . If all predictors within a cluster have already been selected, we start again with the one explaining most of the deviance. Since following this procedure would have made `set3.5` identical to `set3.1`, we replaced `dic_surf_osethz` with the second highest in rank i.e. `log_phosphate`. At the end of the procedure we created 25 different sets as shown in Table B.1.

To better study the predictors and whether there is any clustering or outliers related to the ocean basin they belong to, we conducted a non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS), which is a useful method to reduce the dimensionality of the data and highlights those dimensions which lead to a high discrimination between items (Rabinowitz, 1975). We used the Bray-Curtis dissimilarity index as distance measure, commonly used in ecological studies (Ricotta and Podani, 2017). In our case, this method can also be useful in assessing whether it is necessary to apply spatial data thinning to reduce the confounding effect of autocorrelation (Righetti et al., 2019) or to eliminate some outliers that might bias the models training.

The resulting plot in Figure B.2 highlights that especially the Mediterranean Sea and partially the Southern Ocean present quite unique environmental conditions compared to the other basins. A later Principal Component Analysis revealed that the Mediterranean Sea is characterized by high salinity and low nutrients, while the Southern Ocean by cold temperatures and high oxygen and nutrients (see Figure B.3 in the Appendix). However, as they represent only a few points, we judged their effect on the learning curves of the models to be negligible. Therefore, we did not apply any spatial data thinning.

Figure 2.6: Dendrogram with the predictors and the DM on the horizontal axis. The red line correspond to the cutting height, whereas the predictors are coloured according to the cluster they belong to. The 3 values inside the brackets are the percentage of deviance explained for the 3 criteria in List 2.2.1, while the value below each predictor is the average between these 3 values.

2.3 Multivariate analysis

In the multivariate analysis we follow the modelling procedure used in SDMs for biological studies (see Benedetti et al., 2021; Knecht, 2022; Righetti et al., 2019) but applied to a non-biological target variable. The goal of the multivariate analysis is to extrapolate the monthly global microplastic concentrations for each of the predictor sets created during the univariate analysis and for each of the machine learning models described in Subsection 2.3.1. At the end, we will therefore produce $5 \times 25 \times 12 = 1500$ maps of microplastic concentrations at a 1° spatial resolution.

In this work we are not interested in studying the seasonal evolution of microplastic concentrations, but rather considering the emerging spatial patterns of microplastic distribution in a reference year. Therefore, all the outputs are yearly averaged before performing the analysis of the results.

2.3.1 Machine learning models

The incredible amount of data generated by multiple fields in the last years together with the computational advances led to the need to find new statistical methods to process them. Statistical learning describes the activity of extracting patterns and trends or understand the message behind the data (Hastie et al., 2016).

Nowadays multiple machine learning algorithms of different complexities are available but all of them share the same purpose of predicting an outcome measurement based on a set of features. The prediction is done based on a training set of data that observe the relationship between the outcome and the feature. Subsequently, based on this data the learner predicts the outcome for new unobserved objects based on the previous training (Hastie et al., 2016).

Below we present the 5 different machine learning models used, highlighting their main characteristics and the setup used for the prediction. All models perform a 5-fold cross-validation by randomly splitting 75% of the data for training and the remaining 25% for testing. The modelling was conducted in the `h2o` (`v3.38.0.1`) library in R (Landry et al., 2018).

Generalized Linear Model (GLM)

GLMs are the simplest models used in this analysis and can be considered as an extension of traditional linear models with the difference being that the response distribution is assumed to belong to the exponential family such as Gaussian, Poisson, binomial, gamma, etc. (Nykodym et al., 2023).

They consist of a linear component, a random component from the exponential family of the dependent variable and a link function which relates the expected value of the response with the linear component (Nykodym et al., 2023). In our setup, we included both first and second-order dependencies on the predictors and assumed a normal distribution of the target variable.

Generalized Additive Model (GAM)

GAMs are a more complex extension of GLMs that include the sum of smooth functions of covariates (Hastie and Tibshirani, 1986). Instead of a simple weight vector like for GLMs, GAMs use non-parametric smoothing functions, whereas the most widely used are cubic regression splines (Hastie and Tibshirani, 1986). This is done by dividing the function into several knots along the predictor range and to then fit piece-wise cubic polynomial functions between the knots (Knecht, 2022). In our setup, we use cubic regression splines and as for the GLMs a normal distribution.

Random Forest (RF)

RFs are more complex machine learning models based on bootstrap aggregation (or bagging) built upon a large number of de-correlated tree with added randomness which are then averaged.

The popularity of RFs come from the fact that they are able to capture complex structures in the data and increasingly decrease the bias as they grow in depth without requiring much calibration (Hastie et al., 2016). However, this ability to capture complex non-linear relationships makes RFs prone to fit the noise in the data and producing too much variance, resulting in poor generalization performance. To avoid this, a balance in the depth and complexity of the tree is needed (Boehmke and Greenwell, 2019c). The depth and complexity of the trees and with it the risk of overfitting can be controlled by the following hyperparameters:

- n_{tree} : indicating the number of trees
- m_{try} : controls the split-variable randomization
- min_{rows} : the minimum number of observations in a leaf to split.
- max_{depth} : the maximum tree depth that can be reached.

- r_{sample} : the row sampling rate, whereas higher values can usually improve training accuracy

In our setup, we used the `h2o` default hyperparameters given in Table C.1. We also tuned the hyperparameters using a random grid search across 10 different models with the possible hyperparameter values listed in Table C.1, whereas the one with the lowest RMSE was chosen. However, this considerably lengthened the calculation time without producing a remarkable difference both in terms of outputs and performance metrics. As a result, we retained the default values.

Gradient Boosting Machine (GBM)

Similarly to RFs, GBMs are also based on multiple decision trees. The main difference is that instead of building multiple deep and independent trees (bagging), GBMs build an ensemble of shallow trees in sequence (boosting), where each tree learns and improves from the previous one (Boehmke and Greenwell, 2019b). In this way, the boosting procedure sequentially classifies different versions of the data, producing a sequence of weak classifiers which are finally combined to return the predictions (Hastie et al., 2016).

Schematically, the model starts by fitting a decision tree. Then, the next one is fitted to the residuals of the previous one and added to the starting tree. Similarly, the next one is fitted to the new residuals and added again, and so on (Boehmke and Greenwell, 2019b).

The term “gradient” comes from the fact that GBMs try to minimize the cost function using a gradient descent approach. This describes the idea of gradually decrease the loss function by changing the parameters until a minimum is reached (i.e. the gradient is zero), corresponding to the solution that minimize the error (Boehmke and Greenwell, 2019b). Thanks to their ability of sequentially improves their performance as new decision trees are added, GBMs are considered today one of the most powerful methods available (Landry et al., 2018). The main hyperparameters that control the tree structure are:

- max_{depth} : the depth of individual trees
- min_{rows} : minimum number of observations in a leaf to split

The main hyperparameters that control the boosting are:

- r_{learn} : learning rate which control the speed and accuracy of the gradient descent
- r_{sample} : the row sampling rate, whereas higher values can usually improve training accuracy
- $r_{samplecolumns}$: the column sampling rate

In our setup, we used the `h2o` default hyperparameters given in Table C.2. We also tuned the hyperparameters using a random grid search across 10 different models with the possible hyperparameter values listed in Table C.2, whereas the one with the lowest RMSE was chosen. However, this considerably lengthened the calculation time without producing a remarkable difference both in terms of outputs and performance metrics. As a result, we retained the default values.

Artificial Neural Network (ANN)

Artificial Neural networks or deep learning are models that try to replicate the structure of our brain by building a network of interconnected neurons. Their ability of using non-linear transformations in a layer-by-layer method (Landry et al., 2018) make ANNs a powerful tool when dealing with complex multidimensional data with many different features such as images and videos or complex problems such as facial recognition (Boehmke and Greenwell, 2019a).

Different architectures exist, but the most common and used ones are feedforward ANNs. The structure is composed by an input layer given by the predictor variables and an output layer which is the outcome of what we want to predict or classify. A customizable number of neurons or nodes organized in a given number of hidden layers lies in between, whereas each node in one layer is connected to all the other nodes in the next layer.

Each node adds all the incoming inputs from the previous nodes multiplied by a certain weight plus an extra bias. The connectivity of the network is determined by the fact that if the input that the node receives is strong enough, an activation function determine if the information of the node can be sent to the next layer (Boehmke and Greenwell, 2019a). The main task of the ANNs is then to adjust the node weights so that the model fits the training data as good as possible in a process known as backpropagation (Hastie et al., 2016).

ANNs are often prone to overfitting and therefore some regularization methods to counter it are applied. One way is to stop the training before reaching the global minimum and the other is to add a penalty to the error function to shrink the weights (weight decay) and filter out the signals that are not important (Hastie et al., 2016). The main hyperparameters that control the structure and the risk of overfitting of ANNs are:

- activation function: the function that determine if one node is active and can pass the information to the next layer
- hidden layer structure: the number of hidden layers with their corresponding number of nodes per layer
- λ_{L_1} : first regularization that adds a penalty to the error function and reduce the risk of overfitting
- λ_{L_2} : second regularization that adds a penalty to the error function and reduce the risk of overfitting

In our setup, we used the `h2o` default hyperparameters given in Table C.3. We also tuned the hyperparameters using a random grid search across 10 different models with the possible hyperparameter values listed in Table C.3, whereas the one with the lowest RMSE was chosen. However, this considerably lengthened the calculation time without producing a remarkable difference both in terms of outputs and performance metrics. As a result, we retained the default values.

2.3.2 Environmental driver analysis

To assess and analyse the environmental drivers of microplastic in the models, we focus on these 3 aspects:

1. Partial dependence plot (PDP) curves

In order to study how the models predict the microplastic concentrations, we analyze the shape of the response curve for each predictor and for each model. We extract at 50 points along the predictor range the microplastic predictions, while keeping all the other predictors constant at their mean values. By connecting the 50 points we finally get an impression of how each model capture the mathematical relationship between the predictors and the target variable. The shape of the curve is an indicator of the type and strength of the relationship between the explanatory variables and the target variable.

2. Predictor importance

Here we want to determine how much each predictor contributes to the model predictions. In this analysis we focus only on the relative importance of the 6 predictors of the chosen set (set6.2) given by the more complex models RF, GBM and ANN. The importance of the variables is automatically calculated by the R package `h2o` using different methodologies depending on the model chosen. The variable importance for the tree-based models (RF and GBM) is determined by evaluating whether at each node that variable was selected to split on during the tree building and how much it contributed to the error improvement or worsening (Malohlava et al., 2023). This returns an absolute value which can be scaled to express the relative importance in percentage of each predictor. For ANN the variable importance is computed using the Gedeon method (Gedeon, 1997), which considers the weights that connect the input features in the hidden layers (Candel et al., 2015). The metric is already scaled and can be expressed as relative importance in percentage terms.

3. Environmental conditions in the predictor space

To study the relationship between the most important variables of the chosen set and microplastic concentrations, we graphically represent the microplastic concentrations predicted by the chosen set in a two-dimensional predictors space. Both the predictions and the predictor fields were annually averaged. This allows us to better understand which environmental conditions are associated with the accumulation or dispersion of microplastic.

2.4 Validation and uncertainty

2.4.1 Model performance

A crucial step in any modelling procedure is to quantitatively assess the quality of the model predictions compared to the observations, which are considered as the ground truth. This will ultimately lead to the decision whether the model is validated, i.e. the results are judged as satisfactory and also allows to compare the quality of several models and/or outputs with each other.

To evaluate the model performance, we chose 5 different common goodness-of-fit metrics based on the comparison between observations and predictions. The decision to use multiple metrics stems from the fact that different models have different error distributions (Hodson, 2022) and there is not an objective and universal measure that is better than the others to evaluate the performance. Below we describe the main features of these metrics.

The first two of them report an absolute error estimate by judging how far the predictions (SIM) are from the observations (OBS). The third is similar but provides a relative error estimate in percentage terms. The fourth one gives a quantitative frame on the variance explained by the model. Finally, the fifth informs us about the performance improvement over a null model.

It is important to note that 3 of these metrics (indicated with the underscore $_{test}$) are calculated as the average outcome obtained using five different versions of the training and testing data in the cross-validation process. Comparing the testing metrics with the training metrics gives an impression of the generalization ability of the model. A considerable drop in the performance metrics between training and testing indicates that the relationship learned by the model is spurious and that overfitting is likely occurring. On the other hand, the remaining two metrics are calculated using all the available observations.

1. $RMSE_{test}$ - Absolute error estimate

An accurate model prediction is characterized by a small absolute difference between the predicted and the observed values, i.e. the error. RMSE is a standard statistical metric used in multiple fields that computes the root of the mean squared error (Hodson, 2022). Mathematically, it is defined as:

$$RMSE_{test} = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(SIM_i - OBS_i)^2}{n}} \quad (2.3)$$

Consequently, the computation returns a metric expressed in the same units as the observations and ranging from 0 to $+\infty$, whereas 0 indicates a perfect model.

2. MAE_{test} - Absolute error estimate

Similarly to RMSE, MAE gives an absolute error estimate but instead of computing the root of the average squared error, it simply calculates the average absolute error as the name suggests. Mathematically, it is defined as:

$$MAE_{test} = \sum_{i=1}^n |SIM_i - OBS_i| \cdot \frac{1}{n} \quad (2.4)$$

Exactly as for RMSE, MAE is expressed in the same units as the observations and ranges from 0 to $+\infty$, whereas 0 indicates a perfect model. An important difference between RMSE and MAE is that the latter is less sensitive to outliers. Because of this higher robustness, Willmott and Matsuura (2005) recommend using this metric arguing that RMSE become increasingly larger than MAE as the variability in the distribution of the errors increases. However, there is no consensus of the most appropriate metric and both metrics are commonly used in environmental studies (Hodson, 2022).

3. *RE* - Relative error estimate

The relative error is the average of the ratio between the absolute errors and the observations. In this way, the error estimate is unitless because the error is scaled by the true value and can be expressed in percentage terms. On one hand, this makes its interpretation easier but on the other hand the metric is heavily biased towards low forecasts and not suitable when large errors occur (Chicco et al., 2021). Mathematically, it is defined as:

$$RE = \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{SIM_i - OBS_i}{OBS_i} \right| \cdot \frac{100}{n} \quad (2.5)$$

4. R^2_{est} - Variance explained

R^2 or coefficient of correlation gives the proportion of the variance in the dependent variable that can be predicted from the independent variables and it can be interpreted as the fraction of the entire variance that the model explains (Chicco et al., 2021). This coefficient is theoretically not lower bounded and reaches a maximum value of 1, which denotes a perfect fit. A value of 0 indicates that the fit is equal to the one with the average line. Similarly to the relative error, this makes its interpretation easier since it does not depend on the magnitude of observations. It is computed as the difference between 1 and the ratio between the mean square error and the total sum of squares. Mathematically, it is defined as:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad (2.6)$$

where y_i are the true values, \hat{y}_i the predicted values and \bar{y} the mean of the true values.

5. *NSE* - Performance improvement over the mean

The Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency (NSE) is a metric developed in the context of hydrological forecasts that compares the model performance against a null model corresponding to the simple average of all the observations (Nash and Sutcliffe, 1970). When the metric is lower than 0, our model is worse than the null model and therefore the null model should be preferred. A value of 0 indicates that the model produces the same error variance as the one in the observations, meaning that it is equally good as the null model. The maximal value of 1 indicates a perfect fit and no error. Mathematically, it is defined as:

$$NSE = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (OBS_i - SIM_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (OBS_i - \overline{OBS})^2} \quad (2.7)$$

2.4.2 Response curves agreement

Besides studying the shape of the response curves given by the different models for each predictor, it is also important to analyze how robust these predictions are depending on the model choice. For this we consider the same PDP curves described above and we evaluate at those 50 points how well the curves of the different models agree. The agreement is assessed by computing the normalized standard deviation between the 5 model response values for each predictor and set and at each evaluation point. The normalized standard deviation is the standard deviation divided by

the mean. In this way, the standard deviation is quantified as a fraction of its mean and can easily be compared.

For each predictor and for all predictor sets, we compute the normalized standard deviation of the PDP curves at each of the 50 evaluation points. Higher values indicate that the 5 models do not agree on the response curve and might denote that the relationship between the predictors and the target variable is not strong enough or that the observations are too sparse to establish a robust relationship.

At this point, we assess (i) the PDP curve agreement for each set as an indicator of which set gives more robust predictions and (ii) the PDP curve agreement for each predictor as an indicator of which predictors show a robust relationship with microplastic. For point (i) we group the normalized standard deviation by set and average the values. For point (ii) we group the normalized standard deviation by predictor and we average the values.

2.4.3 Uncertainty quantification

Quantifying the uncertainty and the contribution of each source to the overall uncertainty is an important step of every modelling procedure. The sources of uncertainty in this work are multiple and are mainly related to the observations, their standardization, the predictors data, the hyper-parameters choice, the model choice and the predictor choice. Some of these aspects are related to the limitations of this thesis and are discussed in Section 4.5. For the sake of time we only quantify the uncertainty coming from the model choice and the predictor choice since these have been found to be major contributors in SDM studies (Buisson et al., 2010; Righetti et al., 2019). In particular we focus on these aspects:

1. Model choice uncertainty: model agreement

We denote robust predictions, if the predicted concentrations are comparable between the 5 different models. To quantify this we average the outputs annually and we calculate the normalized standard deviation between the models at each grid point to then repeat the procedure for each set. In this way we are able to study (i) which geographical areas are characterized by high/low model agreement and (ii) which predictor sets are characterized by high/low model agreement. Regions and predictor sets with less than one normalized standard deviation are evaluated as robust.

2. Predictors choice uncertainty: set agreement

Similarly to what is shown above, we also denote robust predictions, if the predicted concentrations are comparable between the 25 different predictor sets. To quantify this we average the outputs annually and we calculate the normalized standard deviation between the sets at each grid point and for each model. In this way we are able to study (i) which geographical areas are characterized by high/low set agreement and (ii) which models are characterized by high/low set agreement. Regions and models with less than one normalized standard deviation are evaluated as robust.

3. Uncertainty partition

To compare the model choice and predictor choice uncertainty and evaluate which one contributes most to the total uncertainty, we follow a similar uncertainty partition method shown in Fatichi et al. (2016). First, we compute the total uncertainty expressed as the difference between the 95th and the 5th percentile. The percentiles are computed using the entire yearly averaged predictions, meaning that the predictions in every grid cell and for all models and sets are considered. For the model uncertainty we group the entire yearly averaged predictions by set and we calculate the differences between the 95th and the 5th percentile. Then we average the obtained values and we finally divide it by the total uncertainty to quantify the relative model uncertainty. In a similar way, for the predictor uncertainty we group the entire yearly averaged predictions by model and we calculate the differences between the 95th and the 5th percentile. Again, we average the obtained values and we finally divide it by the total uncertainty to quantify the relative predictor uncertainty. The total fractional

uncertainty is then the sum between the model and predictor relative uncertainty. Note that the total fractional uncertainty can reach values greater than 1 if the different uncertainty sources are not independent denoting that the uncertainties are instead correlated (Fatichi et al., 2016).

4. Residual analysis

With residual analysis we refer to the study of the error distributions defined as the difference between model predictions and observations. To this end, we compute an annual average of both the predictions and observations and we subtract the observations from the predictions of each grid cell to obtain the residuals. Therefore, positive/negative residuals indicate that the model is overestimating/underestimating the true value. With this we want to investigate (i) the geographical distributions of the residuals, (ii) patterns of overestimation/underestimation and (iii) the correlation between the residuals and the model predictions. Concerning this last point, a high degree of correlation might indicate that there is a systematic error in the model and that the errors are not independent and normally distributed around 0 as should be. The same analysis will be done for both the ensemble average and the chosen set.

2.4.4 Results comparison

A last step in the validation process is to compare the results against 2 different null models and with the results obtained in another independent study. The comparison against the null models is based solely on performance metrics to assess if our models are performing better than a simple null model.

The first null model (Null model 1) simply consists of the average of all the available standardized observations. Using this average we can then compute the same performance metrics described in Subsection 2.4.1 and compare these metrics with the ones from other model simulations. The second model (Null model 2) consists of the zonal average of all available observations with a latitudinal resolution of 5° , whereas the same performance metrics can be computed and compared.

The maps of Null model 1 and Null model 2 with their corresponding performance metrics are shown in Figure C.1 and Figure C.2 in the Appendix. As expected, we can observe that for all the performance metrics, Null model 2 performs better than Null model 1 because it is more able to capture the spatial pattern of observations. These metrics are then compared with the same metrics computed for each set and model.

Finally, in the discussion we compare the model predictions obtained in a Lagrangian modelling study by Kaandorp et al. (prep). In the research, they use the three-dimensional Lagrangian-Eulerian ocean model OceanParcels (Delandmeter and Van Sebille, 2019) to advect virtual plastic particles in space and time and for different size classes.

The vertical motion is taken into account by parameterizing turbulent mixing and biofouling meaning that the change in buoyancy and plastic loss due to sedimentation is considered in the model. Additional sinks and transport processes like beaching and fragmentation are also parameterized. Moreover, the model includes the plastic sources coming from rivers, coastlines and fishing activities. The riverine input is based on the work by Meijer et al. (2021), the coastlines input is parameterized on the global mismanaged plastic dataset by Jambeck et al. (2015), while the release from fisheries is computed as a function of the fishing hours dataset by Kroodsmas et al. (2018). More details are in Kaandorp et al. (prep).

Their main results are that larger plastics contribute most to the total plastic mass and that the previous annual ocean plastic input were likely overestimated.

To compare their results with our results, we only select the surface plastic concentrations for the year 2015 with size less than 5mm. We then average the values in the different size classes to obtain a mean surface microplastic concentration. Afterwards, we convert the measures from items/m³ to items/km² using the upper cell depth of 5m. Finally, we regrid the dataset to match our 1°

by 1° grid in the WGS84 coordinate system. The resulting map is shown in Figure C.3 in the Appendix. We compare this result with our ensemble average and the chosen set by computing the percentage difference for each grid cell.

Moreover, in the discussion we compare our results in terms of items/km² and total plastics items computed in different ocean basins and seas with some reference values found in the literature. These values are shown in Table C.4.

Chapter 3

Results

3.1 Global patterns of microplastic concentrations

In this section, we present the main outputs of the machine learning models obtained by computing the yearly average of the monthly predictions. On the one hand, we analyse the ensemble mean, i.e. the average of the outputs produced among all 25 predictor sets. On the other hand, the output produced by the set considered best (chosen set) according to the criteria listed in the Subsection 3.1.2. The focus of the analysis is on the spatial distribution of microplastic expressed either as number of items per km^2 or as total count of items per grid cell. The results are visualized through maps.

3.1.1 Ensemble mean

Figure 3.1 shows global maps of the annual microplastic concentrations of the ensemble mean across 25 predictor sets for each one of the five models (GLM, GAM, RF, GBM, ANN). All models present two longitudinal bands of higher concentrations around 30° North and South. In the Northern Hemisphere, the maxima concentrations are higher compared to the Southern Hemisphere with concentrations above $100\,000$ items/ km^2 . The areas with maximum concentrations have a clear quasi-circular shape and are located towards the Eastern Pacific and Eastern Atlantic. These regions are more pronounced in the most complex models (RF, GBM and ANN), while in GLM and GAM the accumulation zones seem to be more smoothed out. In the Southern Hemisphere there is less longitudinal difference and concentrations are on average lower than in the Northern Hemisphere but distributed over a large area along the entire 30th parallel. It is also interesting to note that the zone of greatest accumulation in the South Atlantic extends more towards the Equator than the other two oceans, which are more latitudinally confined. Other accumulation areas are the southern coasts of Australia, the Mediterranean, the Red Sea and the Japanese shores especially for the more complex models.

All models display an equatorial band with lower concentrations, generally at least two orders of magnitude smaller than in the subtropical areas. This minimum is particularly visible in the Pacific, where it stretches from the coasts of South America to almost the coasts of Indonesia. This area appears to be divided by a thin line along the Equator with slightly higher concentrations visible more in the Eastern Pacific. In the Atlantic, the lower concentration areas are more restricted and have an elongated, thin shape, which is split into two along the equatorial line by a strip with higher concentration. In the Indian Ocean, the concentrations are generally low but without a clear minimum zone as for the other basins. Moreover the concentrations near the coasts of India and Eastern Africa are generally higher than in the open ocean.

Above 60° North and South of the Equator the difference between the models is more pronounced. GAM predictions are higher, while GLM predictions are lower compared to other models, whereas the difference is around 1 order of magnitude. The more complex models agree in showing intermediate concentrations around $10\,000$ items/ km^2 with some small scale spatial variability in the

Southern and Arctic Ocean. Among the most complex models, ANN shows lower concentrations above Alaska and Canada compared to RF and GBM. Moreover, the different predictor sets disagree in the predictions near Antarctica and in the Arctic Ocean, as well as in the Baltic Sea and near the Baffin Bay for GLM and GAM (see black points in Figure 3.1). For ANN, the uncertainty due to the predictor sets disagreement is above 0.75 standard deviation in the Baltic Sea and in the East Siberian Sea. The tree-based RF and GBM are on the other hand more robust even at high latitudes since the standard deviation between the 25 predictors sets is always below 0.75.

Figure 3.1: Global ensemble mean microplastic concentrations for five models (Generalized Linear Model, GLM; Generalized Additive Model, GAM; Random Forest, RF; Gradient Boosting Model, GBM; Artificial Neural Network, ANN), averaged across all months. The ensemble mean has been computed across 25 predictor sets. Values are shown as \log_{10} and expressed as items/ km^2 . Black points indicate the regions where the standard deviation between predictor sets > 0.75 , indicating a higher predictor sets disagreement and therefore lower prediction confidence.

Considering the global average concentrations, GLM represents the lower bound with a mean concentration around 12 500 items/ km^2 , while GAM the upper bound with a mean concentration around 28 100 items/ km^2 . The mean concentrations of the more complex models lie in the middle

with mean concentrations around 22 300 items/km² (see Figure C.6). As already mentioned and visible in Figure C.4 and Figure C.5, the average concentrations of GLM and GAM are less stable between the different ensemble members compared to RF, GBM and ANN. Moreover, considering a single set, the spread of concentrations is higher for GLM and GAM compared to the other models (see the grey ribbons in Figure C.5 in the Appendix).

Figure 3.2 shows the map obtained by averaging the 5 different model outputs of Figure 3.1. In the subtropical and equatorial region, the general spatial pattern is similar to the one described above since the models generally agree between each other. In the Southern Ocean the concentrations are closer to the one predicted by RF, GBM and ANN since the lower and higher concentrations by GLM and GAM balance each other by averaging the results. The standard deviation between sets and models is above 0.75 in the Southern Ocean, Arctic ocean, Baltic sea and parts of the Baffin and Hudson Bay denoting a higher disagreement between the sets and/or between the models.

Figure 3.2: Global annual ensemble mean microplastic concentrations across all models and predictor sets. Values are shown as \log_{10} and expressed as items/km². Black points indicate the regions where the standard deviation between sets and models > 0.75 , indicating a higher sets and/or models disagreement and therefore lower prediction confidence.

We also computed the total number of microplastic items per grid cell of the ensemble mean. The resulting maps are shown in Figure 3.3. As expected, the general spatial distribution of the total number of microplastic items reflects the spatial distribution of microplastic concentrations given in items/km² (see Figure 3.1). Here the difference between the high and low concentration zones and the general latitudinal patterns is even more remarked. Also the extent of the accumulation zones in the subtropics is larger. The difference between Northern and Southern Hemisphere in

the subtropical gyres is smaller compared to the concentrations in items/ km^2 . In addition, at very high latitudes we notice that even the high complex models show a decrease in the number of microplastic items, which was less remarked when considering the concentrations per km^2 .

Figure 3.3: Total number of microplastic items for each model, averaged over all months and over all the 25 predictor sets (ensemble mean) and integrated over the grid cell area. Values are shown as \log_{10} and expressed as number of items per grid cell.

3.1.2 Chosen set

Criteria for the chosen set

To choose the best predictor set amongst the 25 available ones, we use several criteria that are considered equally important. The 4 criteria are:

- Accuracy
- Robustness
- Interpretability
- Simplicity

Considering all 4 criteria, we finally choose set6.2 which uses 4 physical and biogeochemical predictors, namely `log_nitrate`, `log_phosphate`, `sss_cci_smos` and `sst_oisstv2`, and 2 transport predictors, namely `currents_direction` and `log_total_currents`. Below we give an explanation of why set6.2 is a good compromise between the 4 criteria listed above.

Regarding the first criterion, set6.2 shows the second best average rank in terms of performance metrics (see Figure 3.12).

Its results are also robust given the low mean normalized standard deviation both between the PDP curves (around 3%, 3rd rank out of 25) (see Figure 3.13) and in the model predictions (around 7%, 14th rank out of 25) (see Figure C.11).

Considering interpretability, we are also able to give a raw interpretation of its predictors and we can explain why there is such a relationship between the predictors and the target variable (see Subsection 3.2.2). Moreover, the least interpretable predictor `dic_surf_osethz` is not included in the set.

Our approach is also to prefer the set that has a good performance with the lowest possible number of predictors in order to avoid overfitting and prefer simplicity over complexity. Since the performances of the sets with fewer than 6 predictors were lower than the others, we could not choose a set with 3, 4 or 5 predictors (see Figure 3.12). Set6.2 shows the second best mean performance but allows us to use one less predictor compared to the set with the highest mean performance (set7.2). As a result, we consider set6.2 as the one that adequately meets all 4 criteria.

Global maps

Figure 3.4 shows the resulting maps of the chosen set (set6.2). Given the fact that the normalized standard deviation between sets is relatively low, it is not surprising that the resulting maps are generally similar to the ones of the ensemble mean in Figure 3.1 and with a clear latitudinal pattern (see Figure C.9 in Appendix). Therefore we refer to most of the comments made in Subsection 3.1.1 with some considerations. First, the hemispheric difference in the accumulation zones are less remarked in the chosen set, meaning that the accumulation zone in the Subtropical Gyres of the Southern Hemisphere have a clearer structure. Second, the concentrations in South East Asia and near Japan are generally higher compared to the ensemble mean.

Higher model disagreement is found in the Southern Ocean and in the Baltic Sea, which also correspond to the regions with higher disagreements between predictor sets for GLM, GAM and ANN in the ensemble mean. It is also interesting to note that a small region around the delta of the Amazon River shows lower confidence.

The map with the average between the models and the integrated number of microplastic items for the chosen set are similar to the ones for the ensemble mean. Therefore we refer again to the remarks given in Subsection 3.1.1, while the maps are visible in Figure C.7 and Figure C.8 in the Appendix.

Figure 3.4: Global microplastic concentrations for the chosen set (set6.2), averaged over all months. Values are shown as \log_{10} and expressed as items/km². Black points indicate the regions where the standard deviation between models > 1 , indicating a higher models disagreement and therefore lower prediction confidence.

3.2 Environmental drivers

In this section we focus on the environmental drivers of microplastic. First, we list the final predictors chosen for the multivariate analysis. Then we show their response curves and we compute their relative importance in the predictions. Finally, we highlight the main environmental conditions associated with high or low accumulation of microplastic.

3.2.1 Predictor choice

Table 3.1: Mean deviance explained at the pixelwise level, deviance explained only by GAM at the pixelwise level and mean deviance explained at the zonal mean (1° latitudinal resolution). The deviances explained that are above 10% are green colored. If a candidate predictor meets all the three conditions listed above it is also green colored and it will belong to the final predictors list. The predictors in red were discarded after a testing stage.

Candidate predictor	Average pixelwise [%]	GAM [%]	Average zonal mean [%]
oxygen	34.0	32.0	42.7
sst_oisstv2	33.2	36.5	38.3
degree_north	28.1	25.8	-
log_nitrate	25.0	25.0	21.2
dist2rivers	23.2	10.3	14.0
dic_surf_osesthz	20.3	20.2	38.7
log_phosphate	20.1	20.4	31.7
log_total_currents	19.7	20.4	24.3
wind_u10_era5	19.1	20.7	11.7
ugos	17.4	24.0	29.1
log_chlorophyll_seawifs	15.0	16.4	2.5
degree_east	13.6	12.3	-
sss_cci_smos	12.5	15.4	18.9
currents_direction	11.6	13.9	28.9
log_EKE	10.9	11.6	5.4
dist2cities	10.4	1.2	11.2
log_mld_soda	7.9	10.5	13.2
wind_divergence	7.3	10.7	25.1
log_fishing_hours	6.7	6.7	6.7
wind_direction	4.9	6.5	3.7
bathymetry_min_etopo1	4.2	3.6	19.3
dist2coast	3.2	0.5	4.6
relative_vorticity	3.0	5.5	10.5
wind_v10_era5	2.6	4.8	13.8
vgos	0.8	1.1	24.8
windspeed_era5	0.6	0.8	9.2
divergence	0.2	0.5	6.1
sla	0.0	0.0	14.1

After the univariate analysis described in Section 2.2, we end up with a set of 13 final predictors out of the 28 candidate predictors, which are green colored in Table 3.1.

After a testing phase, we decided to further eliminate three predictors even though they met the three selection criteria. In fact, the three variables `degree_north`, `degree_east` and `dist2rivers`, even in combination with other predictors, create unlikely outputs of microplastic concentrations with

discontinuity and patchy patterns. We could not find a clear reason behind the peculiar behaviour of `degree_north` and `degree_east` and even by changing the range from -180:180 to 0:360 or by computing the cosine, the problem persisted. For `dist2rivers`, the problem seems related to the fact that the variable itself is patchy in space. Therefore we decided to discard them and colored them in red in Table 3.1.

As a result, the list of final predictors used for the modelling stage is limited to 10 variables. There are 6 physical and biogeochemical predictors, 3 transport predictors and only 1 atmospheric predictor, whereas no variables in the category of bathymetry, biological activity, human activity and location were chosen.

The predictor that explains the highest percentage of deviance on average at the pixelwise level is oxygen. The predictor `currents_direction` is the one that explains the lowest percentage of deviance among the final predictors. From Table 3.1, we also notice that `log_chlorophyll_seawifs` and `log_EKE` explain more than 10% of the deviance at the pixelwise level but not at the zonal average level and were therefore discarded. In contrast, the predictors `log_mld_soda`, `wind_divergence`, `bathymetry_min_etopo1`, `relative_vorticity`, `wind_v10_era5`, `vgos` and `sla` have a deviance explained above the threshold at the zonal average level but not at the pixelwise level and were also discarded. The predictor `dist2cities` is the only one above 10% at the average pixelwise and at the zonal average level but not for GAM at the pixelwise level and was also discarded.

3.2.2 Response curves

The partial dependence plots (PDP) of the final predictors and the modelling done by GLM and GAM during the univariate analysis are shown in Figure 3.5. All the final predictors have some degree of interpretability in relation to microplastics. The dissolved inorganic carbon is perhaps the least easily interpretable. Although some studies have shown that the degradation of microplastics in seawater can release organic and inorganic carbon (Novotna et al., 2022; Romera-Castillo et al., 2018; Ward et al., 2019), it is surprising how the relationship is so linear and positive on such a large scale (see Figure 3.5). We suspect, therefore, that this predictor is rather indicative of oceanic gyres (Gregor and Gruber, 2021) and is potentially correlated with another predictor that better explains the distribution of microplastics.

Dissolved oxygen concentrations and sea surface temperatures are highly negatively correlated and both are indicative of the strong latitudinal gradient that is found in microplastic concentrations (Fabri-Ruiz et al., 2023). In fact, the 3 variables (oxygen, `sst_oisstv2` and `degree_north`) that explain most of the variability have a clear latitudinal pattern.

The nutrients nitrate and phosphate are also indicator of the oligotrophic zones in the gyres (Righetti et al., 2019) and therefore have a certain degree of correlation with microplastic. In fact, the curves in Figure 3.5 confirm that the areas with a lower concentration of nutrients have a higher concentration of microplastics, although the models do not agree when nutrients are very low. High nutrient concentrations are indicative of bays, coasts (Ding et al., 2022b) and rivers which can be associated with increased plastic inputs to the ocean (Fabri-Ruiz et al., 2023). However, this smaller-scale effect is not visible in our data. The sea surface salinity includes the effects of latitude, water masses and basin which can explain the spatial pattern of microplastic.

It is not surprising that also 3 predictors associated with ocean dynamic explain a considerable fraction of the deviance in our models, given the importance of currents in creating plastic accumulation zones in the oceans. We expect to have more plastic accumulation where the oceanic geostrophic currents are weak but the Ekman transport is convergent such as in the Subtropical Gyres (Van Sebille et al., 2020). Geostrophic currents alone do not lead to plastic accumulation but they largely influence the shape of microplastic distribution (Onink et al., 2019). The modelled curves between microplastic and total geostrophic currents in Figure 3.5 confirms our expectation, since the relationship is negative.

Looking at the eastward component of the geostrophic current alone (`ugos`), we see that the highest microplastic concentrations are located around zero. This is also meaningful since the strongest

zonal velocity are found around the Equator where microplastic concentrations are typically low. The geostrophic current directions are expressed in radians where π ($-\pi$) correspond to a current with only an eastward (westward) component. The relationship in Figure 3.5 is not so clear, but both GLM and GAM seem to agree in showing that lower concentrations are found where the currents are coming from south ($-\frac{\pi}{2}$) and larger when coming from north ($\frac{\pi}{2}$). We interpret this variable as useful in differentiating between equatorial and subtropical oceanic circulation and therefore able to capture the presence of accumulation zones.

Figure 3.5: Partial dependence plot (PDP) showing the relationship between the target variable and the different predictors separately in the univariate analysis. The red and blue curves show the modelling of the quadratic GLM and GAM, respectively. The boxes show the percentage of deviance explained by the two models.

There is a close relationship between wind and oceanic motion. Wind exerts a direct drag force on the floating surface (windage) influenced by the geometric characteristics of the drifters (Van Sebille et al., 2020), induce Stokes drift by wind waves and most importantly generate Ekman currents that in turn are responsible for the anticyclonic or cyclonic gyres formation (Maximenko et al., 2012). As already indicated, wind also influences the distribution of particles in the upper water

column through wind-driven mixing (Kukulka et al., 2012). It is remarkable that as for geostrophic currents, the eastward component is more related to microplastics compared to the northward component. In particular, higher microplastic concentrations are located where the zonal wind is close to zero (see Figure 3.5). This is not unexpected when considering Sverdrup relation to explain gyres formation. The theory in fact states that the maximal wind divergence in the transition region between the large-scale trade winds and the easterlies (corresponding to a zonal wind component close to zero) generates a convergence of the Ekman transport. In turn, this convergence induces the Ekman pumping and the Sverdrup meridional transport, which leads to the formation of the subtropical gyre circulation (Talley et al., 2011). In contrast, at the Equator, trade winds have a strong negative zonal component and indeed lower microplastic concentrations are observed. The predictor is again indirectly related to subtropical gyres and therefore to microplastic.

Figure 3.6: PDP curves of the different models for each predictor in the chosen set (set6.2)

Figure 3.6 shows the partial dependence plot (PDP) curves of microplastic concentrations on the 6 predictors used in the chosen set and for the 5 models in the multivariate analysis. Considering `currents_direction`, the curves of the most complex models are similar to the curves of GLM and GAM in the univariate analysis (see Figure 3.5). The curves seem to agree in showing that lower concentrations are found where the currents are coming from south ($-\frac{\pi}{2}$) and larger when coming from north ($\frac{\pi}{2}$), although the relationship seems to be relatively weak compared to the other variables.

The relationship of the 2 nutrients `log_nitrate` and `log_phosphate` are instead clearer. All the models agree in identifying a general decrease of microplastic concentrations as nutrient concentrations increase. Nevertheless, the models do not agree in the response curve when the nutrient concentrations are very low. The largest disagreement is between GLM and GAM for `log_nitrate` and between ANN and GLM for `log_phosphate`.

Considering `log_total_currents`, the models disagreement is much smaller and confirms the relationship found during the univariate analysis of a general decrease of microplastic concentrations as the currents velocity increases. For `sss_cci_smos` the relationship is less clear, although the curves show higher microplastic concentrations for very high (around 37 psu) or intermediate (around 33/34 psu) salinity values.

Finally, the response curves of the 5 models largely agree for `sst_oisstv2` above 20°C and highlight higher concentrations around 23°C and then a decrease as the temperature increases. In the colder water below 20°C , the curves are less consistent between the models. GLM shows a continuous

increase of microplastic until around 15°C and subsequently a rapid decrease. GAM instead sees a continuous increase in microplastic concentrations even at very low temperatures. On the other hand, ANN indicates a continuous decrease in the concentrations for temperature below 20°C. RF's and GBM's response curves remain instead quite flat in the colder waters. In general, the response curves are more divergent in the outer predictor ranges.

3.2.3 Predictor importance

Having studied how models determine the relationship between predictors and microplastic, we now want to understand which variables play a more important role during modelling. For this we consider the relative importance of the 6 predictors of the chosen set (set6.2), calculated following the method described in Subsection 2.3.2. The relative importance that each of the 3 most complex models (RF, GBM and ANN) assigned to each of the predictors in the chosen set is shown in Figure 3.7.

In the figure, we can see that physical and biogeochemical predictors are on average more important than transport predictors. The predictor with the highest relative importance is `sst_oisstv2` with a percentage importance ranging from 20% for ANN to 40% for GBM. Then we find `sss_cci_smos` with a mean importance between the models of 19%. Furthermore, we can see that for ANN, salinity has the most important role out of all predictors. The nutrients `log_phosphate` and `log_nitrate` have a mean relative of importance between the models of 18% and 14% respectively. Interestingly, RF gave more weight to nitrates (19%) than phosphates (14%), while GBM gives much more importance to phosphates (21%) than nitrates (7%). Finally, the transport predictors `log_total_currents` and `currents_direction` have a mean importance between the models of 10% and 9% respectively. GBM in particular gives very low importance to these two predictors (4% to `log_total_currents` and 5% to `currents_direction`).

Figure 3.7: Relative importance in percentage terms of each predictor in the chosen set (set6.2) as given by RF, GBM and ANN. The predictors are sorted with increasing relative importance from left to right.

3.2.4 Environmental conditions in the predictor space

To investigate which environmental conditions are associated with high or low microplastic concentrations, we plot the predictions of the chosen set in a two-dimensional predictor space.

The first predictor space that we consider consists of the two most important variables found in the above Subsection 3.2.3, namely `sst_oisstv2` and `sss_cci_smos`. Figure 3.8 shows that higher microplastic concentrations are associated with temperate waters between 20 and 25°C and high salinity between 35 and 39 psu. Lower concentrations are found instead either in very warm tropical waters or very cold polar waters with low salinity.

Similarly, we consider the predictor space composed by the the most important variable overall `sst_oisstv2` and the most important nutrient `log_phosphate`. The results are displayed in Figure 3.9. First, we notice the clear relationship between the two variables, showing a trend of increasing `log_phosphate` with decreasing `sst_oisstv2`. Second, we find that the highest concentrations of microplastics are found in temperate (20-25°C) and nutrient-poor (less than 0.4 mmol/kg) oceanic regions. Lower concentrations are associated instead either with very warm tropical waters or with very cold polar waters and higher phosphate concentrations. Particularly low microplastic concentrations are located in very warm and phosphate-rich waters. GLM also highlights very low microplastic concentrations in very cold and very phosphate-rich waters.

Finally, we consider the predictor space composed by one of the most important variable overall (`sss_cci_smos`) and the most important variable in the transport category (`log_total_currents`). Figure 3.10 highlights that the highest microplastic concentrations are located in the high salinity (35-39 psu) and low currents velocity (below 0.05 m/s) areas. Other areas with still rather high salinity (around 35 psu) but faster currents (above 0.2 m/s) have instead the lowest concentrations. GLM also presents a band with very low microplastic concentrations even at very slow currents velocity and salinity around 34 psu.

Figure 3.8: Modelled concentrations by the chosen set (set6.2) in the predictor space. Sea surface salinity (units in psu) is displayed on the x-axis, sea surface temperature (units in °C) on the y-axis.

Figure 3.9: Modelled concentrations by the chosen set (set6.2) in the predictor space. Phosphate concentration is displayed on the x-axis (units in mmol/kg), sea surface temperature (units in °C) on the y-axis.

Figure 3.10: Modelled concentrations by the chosen set (set6.2) in the predictor space. Geostrophic current velocity is displayed on the x-axis (units in m/s), sea surface salinity (units in psu) on the y-axis.

3.3 Validation and uncertainty

3.3.1 Model performance

In this subsection we focus on the performance of the different sets and models and we compare their accuracy against two null models and the mean between all the models of the ensemble mean. Figure 3.11 gives an overview of the performance measured with the 5 metrics explained in Subsection 2.4.1 for each set and model. To facilitate the comparison, we consider the ranking instead of the metric value as it is. Low ranks indicate a better performance.

From the figure, we can give 3 general considerations regarding the comparison within the models, within the sets and with the ensemble mean and the null models. First, we can see that irrespective of the performance metric, the ranks are quite high in the two simplest models GLM and GAM, they reach a minimum with RF and rise again with GBM and ANN although remaining generally lower than in the simplest models. This suggests that in general RF is the most accurate model, but we will return to this point in a moment.

Second, we can notice that the number of predictors is important in determining the performance. In fact, within a same model the sets with lower number of predictors tend to have a higher rank, while the sets with higher numbers of predictors tend to have a lower rank. This relationship between the number of predictors and the model's accuracy is illustrated more clearly in Figure C.10 in Appendix. Clearly the metric value is improving as the number of predictors is increasing. However, the shape of the curves suggests that the largest improvement is reached when we increase the number of predictors from 3 to 4, while adding more predictors than 6 does not considerably improve the accuracy. We therefore believe that the ratio of the chosen number of predictors to the available data is correct for this work as adding more predictors would not significantly improve the performance and could cause other problems such as overfitting. Consequently, the option of using the chosen set 6.2, which uses 6 predictors, also seems appropriate to have a good balance between accuracy and minimum possible number of predictors. The performance metrics of the chosen set are listed in Table 3.4.

Third, from Figure 3.11 we can compare if a given model and set is better than the 2 null models or the ensemble mean by evaluating if the point lies above the horizontal line (worse) or below the corresponding horizontal line (better). Starting from Null model 1 (mean of all observations), we can see that most of the models and sets perform better than it. Only some sets of GLM for the metrics RMSE, MAE and R^2 show a worse performance. Considering a more complex null model like Null model 2 (zonal average of all observations), we can see that more models and sets have a lower accuracy than it compared to Null model 1. In particular GLM turns out to be almost always worse than Null model 2, except for a few sets with many predictors in the NSE metric. Also GAM is generally inferior except for some sets with many predictors in the R^2 and NSE metric. For the more complex models, the situation seems to be more related to the set choice and the corresponding number of predictors. For ANN, depending on the metric, most of the sets with 5 or more predictors perform better than Null model 2. For the tree-based models, also sets with 4 predictors are usually better. In particular, we can notice that for RF, all sets are better than the null model in terms of NSE and RE and only one set is worse considering R^2 . In terms of RMSE and MAE, only a few sets with 3 predictors are less accurate. For GBM, only one set and two sets are worse than the null model in terms of NSE and R^2 respectively. For the other metrics, also sets with 4 predictors are sometimes worse than Null model 2.

The ranking of the ensemble mean is for most of the metrics better than the one of Null model 2. We can notice that all sets of GLM and GAM are always worse than the ensemble mean. Compared to ANN, only a few sets with 6 or more predictors perform better. For GBM, also sets with 5 predictors are better. All sets of RF are better than the ensemble mean only in terms of RE. In terms of NSE, only one set with 3 predictors is worse. For the other metrics, also several sets with 4 predictors are more accurate.

Figure 3.11: Ranking in the performance metrics for each model and set and compared with the performance of the null models and the ensemble average. The lower the rank, the better the performance.

Table 3.3: Average rank across performance metrics and sets for each model. The models are ordered from best (top) to worst (bottom)

Model	Average rank
RF	22
GBM	38
Ensemble average	40
Null model 2	61
ANN	62
GAM	92
GLM	107
Null model 1	117

By averaging the ranks across the different performance metrics and sets for each model, we are able to evaluate which model is on average more accurate and if they are better than the null models and the ensemble mean. The result of this is shown in Figure 3.3.

As expected from the previous discussion, all models are on average better than the simple Null model 1. On the other hand, only RF and GBM are better on average than Null model 2, although ANN is very close and therefore comparable to this null model. The tree-based models are also the only models which are on average better than using the ensemble mean. Among the 5 machine learning models, RF is the best in terms of accuracy followed by GBM, ANN, GAM and finally GLM. Therefore there is a considerable gap between the more complex models and the simpler ones, with the tree-based models being the best.

Similarly, by averaging the ranks across the different performance metrics and models for each set, we are able to evaluate which set is on average more accurate and if they are better than the null models and the ensemble mean. In Figure 3.12, we can see that all the sets are on average better than Null model 1. Instead, Null model 2 is located mid-table and is better than all sets with 3 or 4 predictors and some sets with 5 predictors. In contrast, all sets with 6 or more predictors have a better average rank.

Interestingly, the ensemble mean has the best average rank compared to all sets. This suggests that even considering the average of several sets and models can give good results despite the fact that, as shown above, RF and GBM alone are on average better. Among the sets, the best rank is obtained by set7.2 followed by set6.2, set7.5 and set6.5. This again shows that a set with a lower number of predictors can give comparable or even better results. For example, a set with 5 predictors (set5.5) ranks better than a set with 7 predictors (set7.3). At the bottom of the table, in contrast, it is clear that 3 predictors do not produce good results since the last 4 places in the ranking are occupied by sets with 3 predictors.

	Set	avg_rank
1	Ensemble_average	40.20
2	set7.2	46.80
3	set6.2	47.56
4	set7.5	48.56
5	set6.5	51.04
6	set7.1	52.60
7	set7.4	52.72
8	set6.4	53.36
9	set6.1	53.76
10	set5.5	56.80
11	set7.3	57.20
12	set6.3	58.64
13	set5.2	59.60
14	Null_model2	60.60
15	set4.5	61.08
16	set5.1	62.84
17	set4.2	63.64
18	set5.4	64.12
19	set5.3	68.04
20	set4.1	70.48
21	set4.4	75.00
22	set3.2	75.52
23	set4.3	76.04
24	set3.5	79.20
25	set3.1	79.80
26	set3.4	89.52
27	set3.3	103.76
28	Null_model1	116.80

Figure 3.12: Average rank across performance metrics and models for each set. The sets are ordered from best (top) to worst (bottom)

Table 3.4: Performance metrics of the chosen set (set6.2) for the different models. The last row shows the performance metrics obtained using the ensemble average (average of all sets and models)

Model	$RMSE_{test}$	MAE_{test}	RE	R^2_{test}	NSE
GLM	1.36	1.15	9.31	-1.62	0.63
GAM	0.47	0.37	8.98	0.69	0.66
RF	0.32	0.22	3.02	0.85	0.93
GBM	0.36	0.26	5.12	0.82	0.86
ANN	0.43	0.34	8.02	0.74	0.74
Ensemble average	0.41	0.31	7.32	0.80	0.75

3.3.2 Response curves agreement

We now consider only the agreement between the models in the response curves of each predictor for all sets. Figure 3.13 shows the mean normalized standard deviation between PDP curves as an indicator of model agreement. The plot highlights that there is a considerable variability across the sets. This is due to the fact that, as we noted earlier, some predictors show less agreement between the response curves than others. The presence within a set of one or more of these predictors consequently leads to an increase in the average disagreement within the set.

However, it can be seen that the agreement in the response curves (corresponding to a decrease in the normalised standard deviation) tends to increase as the number of predictors increases. For example, most sets with 6 or 7 predictors turn out to be below the mean across the sets (see the blue line in the figure), whereas most sets with 3, 4 or 5 predictors turn out to be above the mean. Despite this general trend, it cannot be excluded that some sets with few predictors may have a very low normalised standard deviation as in the case of set3.4. We can explain this general trend in two ways. First, the response curves of a single predictor may change between sets due to the stochasticity inherent in the model training process, which leads to some changes in the agreement between models. Second, a small number of predictors in the set increases the chance that a single predictor with much disagreement will increase the average disagreement within the set. In the case of sets with a larger number of predictors, the presence of one or more predictors with much disagreement is balanced by the others. Comparing the different sets, we can see that set3.1, set3.5 and set4.1 have the highest normalised standard deviation values and thus the highest model disagreement, while set3.4, set5.2 and set6.2 stand out as having more robust response curves. Indeed, the high agreement of the PDP response curves between the models in set6.2 contributed to its selection as the best set (see Subsection 3.1.2).

We now conduct a similar analysis but considering the mean normalised standard deviation for each predictor as illustrated in Figure 3.14. Oxygen, ugos and log_phosphate are clearly the predictors where model response curves are most uncertain. These 3 predictors are characterised by much disagreement in the outer predictors range, especially between GLM, GAM and ANN. In turn, this disagreement in the PDP curves may result in a decreased robustness in the predictions in the regions where the environmental conditions are usually extreme. Therefore the predictors choice not only influences the predictions of the models alone, but also their uncertainty. In fact, high disagreement between the response curves at the extremes of the environmental conditions will result in high uncertainty between the models in these regions. We will discuss the uncertainty in the model predictions in Subsection 4.4.

After these we find in order sst_oisstv2, dic_surf_osethz, log_nitrate and sss_cci_smos. These predictors also show a high disagreement in the outer predictor ranges, but this is mainly limited to one of the two extremes. Finally the higher model agreement is found for two predictors in the transport category and one in the atmospheric category, namely log_total_currents, currents_direction and wind_u10_era5. The response curves for these predictors are less dispersed

even in the outer predictor range helped by the fact that there are more observations even at extreme values. Given these considerations, it is not surprising that the chosen set has low disagreement between the response curves. In fact, it does not contain the 2 predictors with the highest disagreement (ugos and oxygen) and at the same time it contains the two with the highest agreement (current_direction and log_total_currents). Similarly, set3.4 also presents very high agreement since it contains wind_u10_era5, currents_direction and sss_cci_smos.

Figure 3.13: Mean normalized standard deviation between PDP curves for each set. Low values indicate a higher mean agreement between the models in the response curve

Figure 3.14: Mean normalized standard deviation between PDP curves for each predictor. Low values indicate a higher mean agreement between the models in the response curve

3.3.3 Uncertainty quantification

Model choice uncertainty

Figure 3.15: Normalized standard deviation between models for each set. Low values indicate a higher agreement between the models in the predictions

To quantify the agreement between the predictions of the various models, we consider the normalised standard deviation calculated at each grid cell. In turn, this metric can be interpreted as an indicator of the robustness of the predictions and thus of the uncertainty resulting from the model choice.

The resulting maps in Figure 3.15 show that there are recurring geographical patterns of uncertainty between the sets. The highest uncertainties are found at the poles of both hemisphere denoting higher model disagreement. Other areas of high uncertainty are located around the Equator, especially in the Eastern and Western Equatorial Pacific. In the Atlantic, higher disagreement is found in the region of the South Atlantic Subtropical Gyre, while in the Indian Ocean around the equatorial line. The Hudson bay and the Baltic Sea are also areas of high uncertainty for many sets.

Despite these geographical differences, all sets have a maximum normalised standard deviation of less than 0.3 and a median value of less than 0.06 (see Figure C.11 in Appendix). The above-mentioned sets with low uncertainty in the polar regions have a maximum value of less than 0.15 and a median value of less than 0.05. For the chosen set (set6.2) the maximum value is below 0.18 and the median value below 0.04, which is relatively low compared to other sets. The mean value across all sets is 0.066. This means that the divergence between the models is on average less than 7% of the mean value predicted by the models and the maximum is lower than 30%.

Predictor choice uncertainty

In a similar manner, to quantify the agreement between the predictions of the different sets, we consider the normalised standard deviation calculated at each grid cell. Again, this metric can be interpreted as an indicator of the robustness of the predictions and thus of the uncertainty resulting from the predictor choice.

The maps in Figure 3.16 show the resulting geographical distributions of the uncertainties for each model. Overall, the highest disagreement between the sets is found for GLM at latitudes poleward of 60°N/S. A similar pattern can also be seen for GAM, although the uncertainty in the polar regions is smaller compared to GLM. Both models also display high uncertainty but still lower than in the polar regions in huge areas of the tropical oceans, the Indian Ocean and in the Baltic Sea and the Hudson Bay.

The geographical patterns of RF and GBM are really similar and both show that their robustness is generally higher than the simpler models especially at the poles. RF and GBM both indicate that the greatest uncertainty lies in the tropical ocean. In the Pacific this is particularly extensive towards the coasts of South America and Central America. Even around Indonesia we can see horizontal bands of greater uncertainty spreading towards the central Pacific. In the Atlantic, considerable areas in the Southern Hemisphere and the eastern part of the basin are in evidence, even very close to the African coasts. The Indian Ocean also shows some disagreement especially in the north-western part, while the semi-enclosed seas have a relatively high agreement.

For ANN the spatial pattern is more complex and it seems to lie in between the simpler models and the tree-based models. In the tropical regions, it is similar to RF and GBM. In the Southern Ocean, the uncertainties are higher than in the subtropics but still much lower compared to GLM and GAM. The highest uncertainties are at higher northern latitudes and in the Baltic Sea. However, in the Arctic Ocean they are not as extensive as in the simpler models. They are particularly high in the Kara Sea, Laptev Sea, East Siberian Sea and in the Chukchi Sea above Alaska, especially along the coasts.

Despite these geographical differences, all models have a maximum normalised standard deviation of less than 0.25 and a median value of less than 0.07 (see Figure C.12 in Appendix). GLM and GAM have the higher median normalized standard deviations (median around 0.066) and the wider spread. Subsequently, we find ANN (median around 0.05) followed by GBM (median around 0.04) and finally RF which has both the lower median value (median around 0.035) and the lowest spread. This highlights the fact that RF is the least sensitive model to the choice of its predictors and consequently the most robust. The mean value across all models is 0.063. This means that the divergence between the sets is on average less than 7% of the mean value predicted by the models and the maximum is lower than 25%.

Figure 3.16: Normalized standard deviation between sets for each model. Low values indicate a higher agreement between the predictors sets in the predictions

Uncertainty partition

Now that we have quantified the uncertainty associated with the choice of models and of predictors, it is useful to compare these two uncertainties in order to assess which contributes most to the total uncertainty.

Comparing the mean value of the normalised standard deviations between the models (0.066) and between the sets (0.063), we can hypothesise that there is no significant difference between the two sources of uncertainty. To test this hypothesis, we followed the procedure explained in Subsection 3.3.3 and based on the method presented in Fatichi et al. (2016).

The result of the procedure with the fractional uncertainty coming from the model choice and from the predictor choice is shown in Figure 3.17. We can see that model choice uncertainty contributes slightly more than predictor choice uncertainty. In fact in percentage terms, the former contributes 63% and the latter 55% of the total uncertainty. However, the difference between the two uncertainties is relatively small and therefore neither source of uncertainty clearly prevails over the other. Moreover, the sum of the fractional uncertainties is above 100%, which denotes that the

two uncertainty sources are to some extent not independent.

In addition, we also tested whether on a monthly scale the situation is different as averaging over the year may have reduced some of the variability, thus changing the contribution of the different sources of uncertainty. As can be seen in the Figure C.13, even at the monthly level, the model choice uncertainty always contributes slightly more to the uncertainty. It is also interesting to note that the difference between the two sources can be more or less large as well as the total uncertainty depending on the month. However, a detailed analysis of the seasonality is beyond the scope of this work.

Figure 3.17: Fractional uncertainty (or relative uncertainty) coming from the model choice and the predictors choice. Total uncertainty represents the sum of the two fractional uncertainties

Residual analysis

In this last part of the uncertainty quantification, we focus on the model errors in order to investigate their distribution and to detect the presence of systematic biases within the models. In this analysis we only deal in depth with the residuals of the chosen set, as most of the considerations made also apply to the residuals of the ensemble mean.

We start with an analysis of the spatial distribution of the residuals visible in Figure 3.18. We can see that the errors are not randomly distributed in space but appear to be spatially autocorrelated. Moreover, although varying in magnitude, the spatial pattern that emerges is consistent across models. In particular, all the models tend to underestimate in the centres of the Subtropical Gyres. This is evident in the Northern Hemisphere, but it seems to be applicable to the Southern Hemisphere as well, albeit with far fewer observations available. Other areas of underestimation are off the coasts of Japan, in the Bay of Bengal, in the Mediterranean and in the Caribbean Sea. Interestingly, the few points at high latitudes in the Drake Passage show a small error for RF, GBM and ANN but an important overestimation for GAM and especially GLM. The same can be said for the few points near Greenland. There, GLM presents an underestimation, while GAM an overestimation, while the other models show a small overestimation error.

Most of the overestimation areas are instead located in the tropical regions and at the western and eastern edges of the basins in the subtropics. A large part of the areas of overestimation is located

in the tropical region and on the western and eastern edges of the Pacific and Atlantic oceans, as can be seen along the western coasts of Mexico and Canada in the Pacific and those of the Northeastern United States, Northwestern Africa and western of the Iberian Peninsula. Along the entire Australian coasts the predictions are also overestimated, as well as between New Caledonia and New Zealand. Most of the considerations are valid also for the residual maps of the ensemble mean shown in Figure C.14.

Figure 3.18: Geographical distribution of model residuals for the chosen set (set6.2). Red color indicates a model underestimation, while blue colors a model overestimation

We can study the pattern of overestimation and underestimation in more detail by comparing the predictions of the chosen set with the observations as done in Figure 3.19. The closer the predictions are to the identity line, the lower the residuals and the higher the models accuracy. First, the line of linear best fit shows that each model has a tendency to overestimate values when the observed concentrations are low and conversely to underestimate when the observations are high. In the middle range, on the other hand, the predictions do not show such a systematic bias as the predictions are occasionally underestimated and occasionally overestimated.

GLM and GAM are the models that produce the largest absolute errors and that overall are less close to the observations since the line of best fit is on average further away from the identity line. ANN is slightly better but still worse than RF and GBM, which are particularly more accurate especially when the observations are very high. A similar plot is produced when comparing the predictions of the ensemble mean with the observations, as shown in Figure C.15.

Another way of studying the presence of systematic biases is to compare the model residuals with the model predictions. If the model errors are random and independent and without the presence of a systematic bias, no clear trend in the line of best fit should be seen. Figure 3.20 confirms our expectations that the systematic bias of overestimation in low concentrations areas and underestimation in high concentrations areas is present in all models, even though the slope of the lines suggest that the trend is not very strong and the errors are in general random and independent in the middle range. Similar results are obtained with the residuals of the ensemble mean (see Figure C.16 in the Appendix), although the trend is stronger for every model compared to the chosen set.

Figure 3.19: Model predictions of the chosen set (set6.2) against observations. Points closer to the identity line (black line) indicates a smaller error. The blue line represents the linear best fit with the corresponding coefficient of correlation R^2 .

Figure 3.20: Model residuals of the chosen set (set6.2) against model predictions. The points should be randomly distributed around the zero line (black line) and the blue line representing the linear best fit with the corresponding coefficient of correlation R^2 should be flat. This indicates that the errors are randomly distributed and independent.

Chapter 4

Discussion

In this chapter we interpret and discuss the results of extrapolated microplastic concentrations obtained using 5 different machine learning models and 25 predictor sets. We focus on answering the four research questions listed in Section 1.4, comparing our results with other results in the literature and discussing the main limitations and caveats of this work.

4.1 Global spatial patterns

RQ1: What is the magnitude and spatial distribution of surface microplastic concentrations in the ocean? Do the results with machine learning algorithms agree with previous studies?

The magnitude of the annual and global microplastic concentrations averaged across all 25 predictor sets ranges from 10^4 items/km² for GLM to $10^{4.5}$ items/km² for GAM. The more complex models RF, GBM and ANN lie in the middle with mean concentrations around $10^{4.3}$ items/km².

Globally, the ensemble mean for GLM, GAM, RF, GBM and ANN calculates a mean annual microplastic concentration of 10 500 items/km², 31 900 items/km², 22 600 items/km², 22 200 items/km² and 20 700 items/km² respectively at the ocean surface. In addition, we do not observe remarkable differences in the mean concentrations between the Northern and Southern Hemisphere, similar to what found in Eriksen et al. (2014), even though the absolute largest concentrations are found in the Northern Hemisphere (see Figure C.9). The concentrations integrated over the entire ocean surface for GLM, GAM, RF, GBM and ANN suggest that 9 trillions, 14 trillions, 12 trillions, 12 trillions and 11 trillions particles are floating at the ocean surface respectively. These number are similar to the results obtained with Lagrangian simulators in Eriksen et al. (2014) (5.25 trillion particles) and in Van Sebille et al. (2015) (between 15 and 51 trillion particles).

Considering the chosen set (set6.2), GLM, GAM, RF, GBM and ANN calculate a mean annual microplastic concentration of 9100 items/km², 17 000 items/km², 23 500 items/km², 24 300 items/km² and 26 300 items/km² respectively at the ocean surface. In addition, we do not observe remarkable differences in the mean concentrations between the Northern and Southern Hemisphere, similar to what found in Eriksen et al. (2014), even though the absolute largest concentrations are found in the Northern Hemisphere (see Figure C.9). The concentrations integrated over the entire ocean surface for GLM, GAM, RF, GBM and ANN suggest that 9 trillions, 11 trillions, 12 trillions, 13 trillions and 12 trillions particles are floating at the ocean surface respectively. These number are still similar to the results obtained with Lagrangian simulators in Eriksen et al. (2014) (5.25 trillion particles) and in Van Sebille et al. (2015) (between 15 and 51 trillion particles).

Regarding the large-scale spatial distribution, our results show a clear latitudinal pattern (see Figure C.9) of high accumulation in the subtropical gyres and low accumulation in the equatorial and tropical regions consistent with the pattern found using physical models (see e.g. Eriksen et al., 2014; Lebreton et al., 2012; Maximenko et al., 2012; Van Sebille et al., 2015). At higher latitudes,

above the Arctic and Antarctic circle, the predictions are more uncertain but they generally lie in between the high concentrations of the subtropics and the lows of the equatorial zones. In the following, we narrow the spatial scale by focusing on single oceans, seas and bays.

To compare our results with other results found in the literature, we computed the integrated number of particles of our predictions (ensemble mean) for the 5 ocean basins. The ocean with the absolute largest number of floating microplastic items is the Pacific (around 4 trillion particles). This is not surprising since the Pacific covers a much larger area than the other basins. The results are in line with the one found in the modelling study by Eriksen et al. (2014). The Atlantic Ocean has slightly less particles (around 3.5 trillion particles), whereas the smaller surface area is partially balanced by the higher number of items per km^2 . Our predictions are around 3 times larger than estimates found in Eriksen et al. (2014). More complex models project 75% less particles (about 1 trillion items) in Southern Ocean than in the Atlantic and Pacific. The Indian Ocean contains around 1.4 trillion particles, again slightly above the value by Eriksen et al. (2014). Finally, the Arctic Ocean is the basin with the least number of particles (0.35 trillion particles on average) given also the small surface area that it covers.

The comparison with the results by Kaandorp et al. (prep) is in Figure C.17 in the Appendix and is not discussed here. For its discussion we refer to the one made for the chosen set below since it is very similar.

Figure 4.1: Total number of microplastic items for each model, averaged across all months and all the 25 predictors sets (ensemble mean) and integrated over the main ocean basin areas. Values are shown as \log_{10} and expressed as number of items. The position of the “x” correspond to the reference value found in Eriksen et al. (2014) for the comparison. The basins are sorted in ascending order from left to right.

A similar analysis was done but considering the mean microplastic concentrations of our predictions (ensemble mean) and including also bays and seas. Figure 4.2 shows the result of this analysis. Our models show that the highest mean concentrations are in the Mediterranean, and the predictions match the observations given in Pedrotti et al. (2022). The second highest concentrations has been

found in another semi-enclosed sea, the Red Sea. Compared to the observations by Martí et al. (2017), our predictions are around 1 order of magnitude larger. After these two semi-enclosed seas, the third highest concentrations are in the Atlantic Ocean with a mean concentration around 31 500 items/km². Similar results are found also in the Sea of Japan. Here, the concentrations are more than 1.5 orders of magnitude lower than the one observed in Isobe et al. (2015). Afterwards we find the Persian Gulf with a mean concentration of 26 300 items/km²) and the Southern Ocean with mean concentrations around 19 900 items/km² which are 5 times lower than the observations taken near Antarctica by Isobe et al. (2017). The Indian Ocean and the Arctic Ocean have concentrations of around 17 700 items/km². Overall, our predictions for the Arctic Ocean are more than 1 order of magnitude larger than the observations by Yakushev et al. (2021). The ocean basin with the lowest concentrations is the Pacific Ocean with a mean concentration of 16 100 items/km². Lastly, there is the Baltic Sea, the Hudson Bay and the Bay of Bengal. Concentrations of the latter are slightly less than one order of magnitude lower than those found by Sambandam et al. (2022).

Figure 4.2: Global microplastic concentrations for each model, averaged over all months and over all the 25 predictors sets (ensemble mean) and divided and averaged by the main ocean basins and seas. Values are shown as \log_{10} and expressed as items/km². The position of the numbers correspond to the reference value found in the literature for the comparison. The basins/seas are sorted in ascending order from left to right.

We now conduct a similar analysis to the one above but considering the integrated number of particles in the 5 ocean basins as modelled by the chosen set (set6.2). The ocean with the absolute largest number of floating microplastic items is the Pacific (around 4 or 5 trillions of particles depending on the model). This is not surprising since the Pacific covers a much larger area than the other basins. The results are in line with the one found in the modelling study by Eriksen et al. (2014). The Atlantic Ocean has slightly lower concentrations (around 4 trillions of particles), whereas the smaller surface area is partially balanced by the higher number of items per km². Our predictions are around 4 times larger than the ones reported in the literature. Well below we found the Indian Ocean, where there is much more agreement in predicting that the Indian Ocean contains around 1.5 trillion particles, again slightly above the value by Eriksen et al. (2014). Then

there is the Southern Ocean where the predictions span from 0.03 trillions of GLM to 1.3 trillion particles of GBM. Finally, we find the Arctic Ocean with around 0.06 trillion particles.

A similar analysis was done but considering the mean microplastic concentrations of our predictions (set6.2) and including also bays and seas. The Mediterranean (mean concentration of 144 000 items/km²) and the Red Sea (mean concentrations of 48 800 items/km²) have the highest mean microplastic concentrations, exactly the same as for the the ensemble mean. In the Mediterranean Sea the concentrations are again very similar to the observations, while in the Red Sea they are consistently higher. With slightly lower concentrations, we find the Sea of Japan with predicted concentrations of 38 000 items/km² that are more than 1.5 orders of magnitude lower than the ones reported in Isobe et al. (2015) and the Persian Gulf. The ocean basin with the highest concentrations is the Atlantic with a mean concentration around 33 800 items/km² followed by the Indian Ocean and the Pacific Ocean with very similar mean concentrations around 17 500 items/km². The mean concentration in the Arctic Ocean are 16 400 items/km² and are higher than observed in Yakushev et al. (2021). Lower concentrations around 11 000 items/km² are predicted in the Southern Ocean. Lastly, there is the Bay of Bengal with concentrations 84% lower than those found by Sambandam et al. (2022) and the Baltic Sea with a very high disagreement between the models (note that the GAM predictions are not displayed because they were unrealistically high).

Figure 4.3: Total number of microplastic items for each model of the chosen set (set6.2), averaged across all months and integrated over the main ocean basins. Values are shown as \log_{10} and expressed as items/km². The position of the numbers correspond to the reference value found in the literature for the comparison. The basins are sorted in ascending order from left to right.

Figure 4.4: Global microplastic concentrations of the chosen set (set6.2) for each model, averaged across all months and divided and averaged by the main ocean basins and seas. Values are shown as \log_{10} and expressed as items/km². The position of the numbers correspond to the reference value found in the literature for the comparison. The basins/seas are sorted in ascending order from left to right.

We now compare our results of the chosen set (set6.2) with the ones by Kaandorp et al. (prep) at the grid cell level. The relative difference is shown in Figure 4.5. The most striking difference is that for most of the ocean, the predictions of our chosen set are higher than the prediction using a physical model. The percentage difference is particularly high in the equatorial region and the Southern Ocean. It is lower in the subtropical gyres and in the Indian Ocean, where sometimes our predictions are even lower.

Comparing our results in Figure 3.4 with Figure C.3 we can see that the large-scale spatial distribution of microplastic agree with the one in Kaandorp et al. (prep). The main differences are that the concentrations of the latter span a much wider range. Moreover, the North Atlantic Gyre has lower concentrations than the North Pacific and the concentrations in the Indian Ocean and South East Asia are higher. However, we should consider that the data standardization described in Subsection 2.1.2 eliminated any absences of plastic and generally raised the concentrations. Therefore our statistical models are not able to produce such low values in contrast to the physical models. Also we do not have any predictor directly related to the human inputs, which on the other hand is an important component of the physical model. This can explain the lower concentrations in the Indian Ocean and South East Asia, since there the plastic pollution from the coasts are particularly high (Jambeck et al., 2015). These aspects will be discussed also in Section 4.5.

Figure 4.5: Relative difference in percentage terms between the chosen set (set6.2) results for each model and the results by Kaandorp et al. (prep). Purple (red) colour indicates that our models' predictions are higher (lower).

4.2 Environmental drivers of microplastic concentrations

RQ2: What are the main predictors that drive the distribution of surface microplastic concentrations?

In order to identify the environmental drivers of microplastic in the oceans, we started with an extensive review of existing literature and we selected 10 out of 28 variables applying an univariate analysis. All these variables are considered important either because of their direct influence on microplastic distribution or as proxies for causal factors (Lima et al., 2021).

Lagrangian studies using physical models have shown the importance of dynamical variables such as oceanic currents on microplastic accumulation (see e.g. Onink et al., 2019; Van Sebille et al., 2015), while correlative studies suggest the importance of physical and chemical parameters and wind (see Kanhai et al., 2017; Pogojeva et al., 2021). Our list of 10 final predictors indeed include different categories of predictors: 6 predictors are in the physical and biogeochemical category (oxygen concentrations, sea surface temperature, sea surface salinity, dissolved inorganic carbon concentrations, nitrate concentrations and phosphate concentrations), 3 in the transport category (geostrophic current velocity, eastward geostrophic current velocity and currents direction) and 1 in the atmospheric category (eastward wind speed).

All the final predictors have some degree of interpretability in relation to microplastics. The

dissolved inorganic carbon is perhaps the least easily interpretable. Although some studies have shown that the degradation of microplastics in seawater can release organic and inorganic carbon (Novotna et al., 2022; Romera-Castillo et al., 2018; Ward et al., 2019), it is surprising how the relationship is so linear and positive on such a large scale (see Figure 3.5). We suspect, therefore, that this predictor is rather indicative of oceanic gyres (Gregor and Gruber, 2021) and is potentially correlated with another predictor that better explains the distribution of microplastics.

Dissolved oxygen concentrations and sea surface temperatures are highly negatively correlated and both are indicative of the strong latitudinal gradient that is found in microplastic concentrations (Fabri-Ruiz et al., 2023). In fact, the 3 variables (oxygen, sst_oisstv2 and degree_north) that explain most of the variability in the univariate analysis have a clear latitudinal pattern.

The nutrients nitrate and phosphate are also indicators of the oligotrophic zones in the gyres (Righetti et al., 2019) and therefore have a certain degree of correlation with microplastic. The curves in Figure 3.5 confirm that, since the areas with a lower concentration of nutrients have a higher concentration of microplastics, although the models do not agree when nutrients are very low. High nutrient concentrations are indicative of bays, coasts (Ding et al., 2022b) and rivers which can be associated with increased plastic inputs to the ocean (Fabri-Ruiz et al., 2023). However, this small-scale effect is not visible in our data. The sea surface salinity includes the effects of latitude, water masses and basin which can explain the spatial pattern of microplastic.

It is not surprising that also 3 predictors associated with the ocean dynamics explain a considerable fraction of the deviance in our models, given the importance of currents in creating plastic accumulation zones in the oceans (Onink et al., 2019). We expect to have more plastic accumulation where the oceanic geostrophic currents are weak but the Ekman transport is convergent such as in the subtropical gyres (Van Sebille et al., 2020). Geostrophic currents alone do not lead to plastic accumulation but they largely influence the shape of microplastic distribution (Onink et al., 2019). The modelled curves between microplastic and total geostrophic currents in Figure 3.5 confirms our expectation, since the relationship is negative. Looking at the eastward component of the geostrophic current alone (ugos), we see that the highest microplastic concentrations are located around zero. This is also meaningful since the strongest zonal velocities are located around the Equator where microplastic concentrations are typically low. The geostrophic current directions are expressed in radians where π ($-\pi$) correspond to a current with only an eastward (westward) component. The relationship in Figure 3.5 is not so clear, but both GLM and GAM seem to agree in showing that lower concentrations are found where the currents are coming from south ($-\frac{\pi}{2}$) and larger when coming from north ($\frac{\pi}{2}$). We interpret this variable as useful in differentiating between equatorial and subtropical oceanic circulation and therefore able to capture the presence of accumulation zones.

There is a close relationship between wind and oceanic motion. Wind exerts a direct drag force on the floating surface (windage) influenced by the geometric characteristics of the drifters (Van Sebille et al., 2020), inducing Stokes drift by wind waves and most importantly generating Ekman currents that in turn are responsible for the anticyclonic or cyclonic gyres formation (Maximenko et al., 2012). As already indicated, wind also influences the distribution of particles in the upper water column through wind-driven mixing (Kukulka et al., 2012). It is remarkable that as for geostrophic currents, the eastward component is more related to microplastics compared to the northward component. In particular, higher microplastic concentrations are located where the zonal wind is close to zero (see Figure 3.5). This is not unexpected when considering Sverdrup relation to explain gyres formation. The theory in fact states that the maximal wind divergence in the transition region between the large-scale trade winds and the easterlies (corresponding to a zonal wind component close to zero) generates a convergence of the Ekman transport which in turn induces the Ekman pumping and the Sverdrup meridional transport, which leads to the formation of the subtropical gyre circulation (Talley et al., 2011). In contrast, at the Equator, trade winds have a strong negative zonal component and indeed lower microplastic concentrations are observed. The predictor is again indirectly related to subtropical gyres and therefore to microplastic.

The chosen set is composed by 4 physical and biogeochemical predictors and 2 transport predictors. Of these, the predictor with the highest mean relative importance is sea surface temperature

(30%), followed by sea surface salinity (19%), phosphate concentrations (18%), nitrate concentrations (14%), geostrophic current velocity (10%) and finally current direction (9%). Our main environmental drivers correspond to the ones in (Lima et al., 2021), who also found that sea surface temperature, sea surface salinity and current velocity are the most important predictors. They also indicate wind speed to be an important predictor, which indeed has the highest relative importance in the set where it is included as a predictor. Moreover, nitrate concentrations have been found to be among the best predictors also in (Fabri-Ruiz et al., 2023).

The most important variable is the one with a strong latitudinal pattern, namely sea surface temperature. This is due to the fact that the spatial distribution of microplastic concentration also has a strong latitudinal pattern (see Figure C.9) and therefore these types of predictors have a stronger correlation with the target variable. The same was observed also in the univariate analysis. For the same reason, oxygen concentrations assume the role of the most important variable in sets where sea surface temperature is not present. It is also interesting to note that there is also a hierarchy according to the category of predictors: the models tend to give more importance to physical and biogeochemical predictors than to transport predictors. This can be explained by the fact that, on average, the latter explain a higher fraction of the deviance than the former in the univariate analysis since they tend to have a stronger latitudinal pattern compared to transport predictors.

The high importance of sea surface temperature and salinity suggests that the physical characteristics of water masses and their interaction are important in determining the accumulation of microplastic as also noted in Lima et al. (2021). Considering the environmental conditions, we found that high concentrations of microplastic are generally associated with temperate waters between 20-25°C, high salinity (35-39 psu), nutrient-poor (less than 0.4 mmol/kg) and slow moving (less than 0.05 m/s), which are common environmental conditions in the subtropical gyres (Melzer and Subrahmanyam, 2017). This generally corresponds to the favourable accumulation conditions highlighted in Lima et al. (2021). However, their results from a GAM indicate the highest accumulation of microfibrils in very cold polar waters (5-10°C). Interestingly, our GAM also predicts very high concentrations in cold regions, which is not confirmed by other models. Further investigations are needed to assess whether this relationship is real or merely a bias of GAM in the outer predictor range.

4.3 The potential of machine learning algorithms

RQ3: Are machine learning algorithms better than null models in extrapolating microplastic concentrations? Which machine learning algorithm performs best?

To answer this question, we considered five performance metrics calculated for each model across all 25 predictor sets. The results show that all models are on average better than the simple null model 1, i.e. the average of all observations. Only GLM and for a few combinations of predictors performs worse. Comparing with null model 2 (zonal average of observations at 5° resolution), only RF and GBM are on average better. ANN, on the other hand, has a comparable but slightly lower performance, while GLM and GAM are clearly worse. We could also find that using the ensemble mean (the average of all models and predictor sets) results in a better performance than GLM, GAM and ANN and worse performance than GBM and RF.

Overall, RF is the best model followed by GBM, ANN, GAM and finally GLM. It can thus be seen that there is a hierarchy based on the complexity of the models. This hierarchy of the performance based on the model complexity is also typically observed in SDMs studies (see Benedetti et al., 2021; Knecht, 2022). In our case, the simpler models such as GLM and GAM are worse than the more complex models. The tree-based models perform better and are more able to capture the complex relationship between the explanatory variables and the target variable. For the chosen set (set6.2) RF has the lowest RMSE (0.32), lowest MAE (0.22), lowest RE (3.02%), highest R^2 (0.85) and highest NSE (0.93).

In addition to the model, the number of predictors used also determines the performance. In general, as the number of predictors increases, the performance increases. However, increasing the number from 6 to 7 predictors did not lead to a considerable improvement in performance. This suggests, according to our analysis and data availability, that 6 predictors is a good compromise between obtaining a good performance and avoiding having too many predictors.

In terms of errors, for all models the relative error never exceeds 12% and is on average below 10% but presents a systematic bias of overestimation of low values and underestimation of high values. This bias is also observed in the study by Fabri-Ruiz et al. (2023) in the Mediterranean. This highlights the fact that our models are not able to reproduce extreme concentration values and given the relative coarse resolution are also unable to reproduce the small-scale variability observed in the ocean (Mansui et al., 2020).

According to our results, the more complex machine learning models have the potential to reliably map global microplastic concentrations since they have better performances than simply computing the average or the zonal average of the observations. This data-driven approach could be favourable considering that it is computationally cheaper than physical models (Sahastrabuddhe and Ghosh, 2021) that are the prevailing approach to date for mapping microplastic concentrations in the oceans. In addition, this approach could benefit from an increasing number of observations in the future.

4.4 Uncertainty

RQ4: How large is the uncertainty due to machine learning algorithm choice and predictors choice?

The highest model uncertainty is located in the Arctic Ocean and in the Southern Ocean, making our predictions above the Arctic and Antarctic circles particularly uncertain. For this reason, the predictions of the chosen set are stippled in the Southern Ocean due to the high standard deviation between the models (see Figure 3.4). Another geographical region with considerable uncertainty, albeit less than the polar zones, is the Eastern Equatorial Pacific. Regions near the deltas of the major rivers, like the Amazon river are also characterized by high uncertainty. The geographical pattern of high model disagreement at high latitudes and in the tropics is consistent with the strong disagreement between 3 physical models found in Van Sebille et al. (2015).

The model choice uncertainty stems from the disagreement in the response curves, which is particularly high in the outer ranges of the predictors (see Subsection 3.3.2). We therefore interpret the high uncertainty in the polar regions as a result of a mix of extreme physical and biogeochemical conditions and scarcity of observations. Indeed, the Polar Seas are characterised by low temperatures, high nutrient and oxygen concentrations and a low number of available observations. This results in a limited number of observations at the outer predictor ranges and thus greater divergence between the learning curves as noted in Figure 3.6. This also explains the higher disagreement near the deltas of the major rivers. In fact, the rivers export high amounts of nutrients such as `log_nitrate` and `log_phosphate` (Masotti et al., 2018) and the disagreement in the PDP curves by the different models (see Figure 3.6) is reflected in rather different predictions.

On the other side, we interpret the higher uncertainty in the equatorial region as coming from the extreme values in the transport predictors. However, the number of observations available in these regions is greater than in the polar regions. As a result, the divergence between the response curves of the transport predictors is smaller than for physical and biogeochemical predictors. So, the uncertainty in equatorial regions, although higher than in other areas, is usually lower than at high latitudes as we can observe from Figure 3.15. Models with relatively high agreement in the polar regions are set3.3, set3.4, set4.3, set5.3, set6.3 and set 7.3. All these sets contain neither `sst_oisstv2` nor oxygen which would otherwise contribute to increasing uncertainty in these regions. In other words, the sets with low model uncertainty in the polar regions have predictors with high PDP curve agreements in the outer predictor ranges.

Quantitatively, the mean normalized standard deviation between the models is on average less than 7%. This means that the dispersion between models represents on average only 7% of the mean value of the prediction. The maximum values of the normalized standard deviation are always less than 30% and confined to the high latitudes. We therefore consider the uncertainty given by the model choice to be considerable only above latitudes of 60°N/S.

The highest predictor choice uncertainty is located in the Arctic Ocean and Southern Ocean making our predictions above the Arctic and Antarctic circles highly uncertain, particularly for GLM, GAM and partially for ANN. This points out that the response curves of GLM tends to largely diverge in the outer predictors range as mentioned before. For certain predictors such as oxygen, ugos and log_phosphate, PDP curves tend to diverge more at the edges of the predictor range and consequently the presence or absence of these predictors within the set leads to discordant predictions between sets. On the other side, the higher robustness at the poles of RF and GBM results from the fact that their response curves are more stable in the outer predictors range and therefore the predictors choice is less crucial for the predictions at the high latitudes. For this reason, the highest predictors choice uncertainty for these models lies in the Eastward Equatorial Pacific, parts of Southern Atlantic and Indian Ocean and not at higher latitudes.

Quantitatively, the mean normalized standard deviation between the predictor sets is on average similar to the one between the models (less than 7%). The maximum values of the normalized standard deviation is slightly below (less than 25%) and confined to the high latitudes, especially for GLM, GAM and ANN in some Arctic regions. We therefore consider the uncertainty given by the predictors choice to be remarkable only above latitudes of 60°N/S.

On both monthly and annual scale, the model choice uncertainty appears to be the main source of uncertainty. This confirms the evaluation of several studies with SDMs which show that model choice is the primary source of uncertainty (Buisson et al., 2010; Diniz-Filho et al., 2009, Knecht, 2022). The difference in regard to predictor choice is however limited to less than 10%, which highlights that also the predictor choice is a major source of uncertainty as found in other SDM studies (Righetti et al., 2019).

4.5 Limitations

Since this work is based on a data-driven approach, the major limitations are due to the characteristics, quantity and quality of the data. Regarding quantity, we could see that the observations of microplastic are biased in both space and time. Consequently, it is not just a question of data quantity but also of how the observations are distributed. In fact, we particularly highlighted the scarcity of observations in the Southern Hemisphere and at high latitudes. This has a direct impact on the training of statistical models. The scarcity of data in certain portions of the environmental space increases the probability that the models fit spurious relationships (Knecht, 2022). Indeed, we argued that the irregular sampling effort is the major cause of the high prediction uncertainty in the Arctic and Southern Ocean.

Regarding data quality, it is known that the method of measurement as well as the setup used during plastic data collection (mesh size, net size, ...) makes it difficult to compare observations between different studies (Pasquier et al., 2022). Indeed, the lack of sampling harmonization across different studies is a known and pressing problem in the field of plastic research (Montoto-Martínez et al., 2022), even though some guidelines have been introduced in recent years (see for example GESAMP (2019) and Miller et al. (2021)). For example, Pasquier et al. (2022) found that even though the Manta net is the most common used device for sampling microplastic, the mesh sizes, trawling duration, speed, distance and net dimensions can strongly influence the measurements. In addition, observations taken with Manta and Neuston nets can already give quite different results given the fact that Neuston nets sample a larger water layer (Pasquier et al., 2022).

Atmospheric and oceanic conditions are also known to have an influence on microplastic observations in the mixed layer (Kukulka et al., 2012). For this reason, we decided to use the standardized observations computed by Van Sebille et al. (2015). Since standardization uses a statistical method

(GAM), the process of standardizing observations introduces uncertainty (see Subsection 2.1.2). Because of all these considerations, the microplastic dataset is a main source of uncertainty of this work.

Regarding the environmental climatologies, we have highlighted the environmental drivers that determine the distribution of microplastic. Unlike physical models that allow us to directly study the dynamical causes that move plastics around the oceans and consider sources and sinks (Maximenko et al., 2012; Onink et al., 2019; Van Sebille et al., 2015), our approach allows us to find statistical relationships that do not necessarily imply direct causality. By interpreting the predictors, we argued that most of them are indicators of subtropical gyres, which in turn are spatially related to plastic accumulation. We must therefore consider these predictors as proxies for causal factors rather than direct causation.

Furthermore, a limitation of this work is the lack of predictors that take into account human sources of microplastic. Indeed, all the predictors related to human inputs (distance to coasts, cities, rivers and fishing efforts) were found to be inadequate, suggesting that further studies are needed. Therefore, we suggest that further investigation to find a suitable predictor based on the mismanaged plastic generated by each country is necessary. This would be particularly useful for improving predictions near coastal areas where plastic input is particularly important such as in South-East Asia (Jambeck et al., 2015; Lang, 2018). Moreover, the ability to predict future changes in microplastic concentrations due to an increase or decrease in mismanaged plastic waste as done in other studies (Lang, 2018) remains limited at present using this approach.

Chapter 5

Conclusion and outlook

5.1 Conclusion

The general purpose of this study was to assess the suitability of different machine learning techniques when predicting global patterns of surface microplastic concentrations. Using an ensemble approach of 5 different models and 25 different predictor sets (using 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7 predictors), we predicted the global monthly distribution of microplastic concentrations at the ocean surface. To this end, we used the most comprehensive observational microplastic dataset compiled by Van Sebille et al. (2015) and different environmental climatologies as predictors.

The first aim of the study was to assess the global spatial patterns of surface microplastic concentrations. The results show high concentrations in the 5 subtropical gyres, the Mediterranean Sea and the Red Sea. Lowest concentrations have been found in equatorial and upwelling regions. In polar regions, we generally predicted intermediate concentrations but those regions are characterized by the highest disagreement between models and predictor sets. The global and annual mean microplastic concentrations range from 9100 items/km² to 26 300 items/km² suggesting that an integrated number between 9 and 14 trillion microplastic particles are floating at the ocean surface, which agree with previous modelling estimates. The latitudinal patterns of accumulation agree with previous studies that use physical models. Compared to observations, the mean relative error of both, the ensemble mean and the chosen set, is below 8% but the errors show a systematic bias of overestimation at low concentrations and underestimation at high concentrations.

The second aim was to identify the main drivers of microplastics. In the univariate analysis, we identified 6 physical and biogeochemical, 3 transport, and 1 atmospheric predictors as the one that explain most of the deviance. Variables with a clear latitudinal pattern such as sea surface temperature and dissolved oxygen concentrations explained the greatest fraction of deviance. In general, physical and biogeochemical variables which are indicative of gyres explained a higher fraction of deviance than transport predictors. In the chosen set (set6.2), consisting of 6 predictors, water mass indicators such as sea surface temperature and salinity were the most important. We found an intermediate importance for the two nutrient variables (nitrate and phosphate) and the least importance for the two transport variables (geostrophic current velocity and current direction). High microplastic concentrations are associated with temperate (20-25°C), high salinity (35-39 psu), nutrient-poor (less than 0.4 mmol/kg) and slow moving (less than 0.05 m/s) waters.

The third aim was to assess the potential of machine learning techniques by comparing their accuracy against two null models (mean of observations, and latitudinal mean of observations). All models are on average better than the simplest null model (mean of observations). The most complex and tree-based models, RF and GBM are also consistently better than the second null model (latitudinal mean of observations), while ANN shows an average performance similar to the second null model. The simplest models GLM and GAM are on average worse than the second null model. Overall, RF has the best performance and explains more than 80% of the variance in the chosen set (set6.2). Moreover, the ensemble mean (prediction mean across all models and sets)

results in a better performance than ANN, GAM and GLM and worse than RF and GBM and explains more than 80% of the variance. Finally, we found that initially the higher the number of predictors, the better the performance. However, after 6 predictors the accuracy does not improve significantly.

The fourth aim was to quantify the uncertainty with regard to model and predictor choice. The highest model and predictor choice uncertainties were found at latitudes higher than 60°N/S in the Arctic and Southern Ocean. The disagreement in those regions can reach 25% of the mean predicted values. The equatorial Pacific and Indian Ocean have a higher than average uncertainty but still lower than in polar regions. The global mean disagreement between models is less than 7% of the mean predicted value and the global mean disagreement between predictor sets is also below 7%. Overall, model choice uncertainty contributes slightly more (63%) to the total uncertainty than predictor choice uncertainty (55%).

5.2 Outlook

We conclude that data-driven methods, albeit with their uncertainties and limitations, have the potential to extrapolate microplastic concentrations on a global scale. We believe that in the future these techniques will benefit from more observations concerning microplastics and may prove attractive due to their relative computational inexpensiveness. Besides the quantification, we hope that the quality of the observations will also improve by uniforming the measurement techniques and homogenising the sampling effort in space and time. In this way, observational data will become more representative of the real situation in the ocean.

This thesis is to be regarded as an exploratory work on the subject and we believe that several improvements and developments can be made in the future. First, it would be appropriate to redo the same analysis but using the non-standardized observations. In this way, the sensitivity of the models to a change in the initial observations could be assessed. Secondly, we believe that further research is needed to find suitable predictors that take into account human plastic release. Our choice of using distance to cities/coasts/river and fishing effort did not lead to good results. Third, in addition to experimenting with further machine learning models, a more comprehensive tuning of the hyperparameters should be included. In this way, one could study the sensitivity of the estimates on the hyperparameter choice.

Appendix A

Data sources

Table A.1: Environmental data sets assembled for the analysis.

Predictor	Unit	Temporal coverage	Original spatial resolution	Reference
Wind speed	m/s	-	1°	Hersbach et al. (2020)
Northward wind speed	m/s	-	1°	Hersbach et al. (2020)
Eastward wind speed	m/s	-	1°	Hersbach et al. (2020)
Wind direction	rad	-	1°	Hersbach et al. (2020)
Water depth	m	-	1°	Amante and Eakins (2009)
Chlorophyll	mg m ⁻³	1997-2010	1°	NASA OB.DAAC (2018)
Fishing hours	hours	2016	0.1°	Kroodsma et al. (2018)
Distance to closest coast	m	-	0.15°	Bathymetry: Amante and Eakins (2009)
Distance to closest largest rivers	m	-	0.15°	Bathymetry: Amante and Eakins (2009), rivers: Fekete et al. (2002)
Distance to closest largest city	m	-	0.15°	Bathymetry: Amante and Eakins (2009), cities: opendatasoft
Sea surface salinity	psu	2010-2012	1°	Olmedo et al. (2017)
Sea surface temperature	°C	1981-2013	1°	Huang et al. (2020)
Nitrate concentrations	µmol kg ⁻¹	1955-2017	1°	Garcia et al. (2019)
Phosphate concentrations	µmol kg ⁻¹	1955-2017	1°	Garcia et al. (2019)
Dissolved oxygen concentrations	µmol m ⁻³	1955-2017	1°	Garcia et al. (2019)
Mixed layer depth	m	-	1°	Carton et al. (2018)
Dissolved inorganic carbon	µmol kg	1982-2020	1°	Gregor and Gruber (2021)
Sea level anomaly	m	1993-2019	0.25°	AVISO (2016)
Geostrophic currents velocity	m/s	1993-2019	0.25°	AVISO (2016)
Northward geostrophic currents velocity	m/s	1993-2019	0.25°	AVISO (2016)
Eastward geostrophic currents velocity	m/S	1993-2019	0.25°	AVISO (2016)
Wind divergence	1/s	-	1°	Hersbach et al. (2020)
Eddy kinetic energy	m ² s ⁻²	1993-2019	1°	AVISO (2016), computed following Qiu and Chen (2004)
Relative vorticity	1/s	1993-2019	0.25°	AVISO (2016)
Divergence	1/s	1993-2019	0.25°	AVISO (2016)
Currents direction	rad	1993-2019	0.25°	AVISO (2016)

Table A.2: Pool of all possible predictors of microplastic concentrations in the ocean. The related literature indicates the papers where a certain relationship between the predictor and microplastic was found.

Predictor	Related literature
Wind speed	Granado et al. (2019); Kanhai et al. (2017); Lima et al. (2021)
Northward wind speed	Lima et al. (2021)
Eastward wind speed	Lima et al. (2021)
Wind direction	Kanhai et al. (2017)
Water depth	Onink et al. (2021)
Chlorophyll	De Botton Falcón (2021); Kanhai et al. (2017); Liu et al. (2022); Sambolino et al. (2022)
Fishing hours	Dowarah and Devipriya (2019); Jorquera et al. (2022); Li et al. (2016); Kaandorp et al. (prep); Zhang et al. (2021)
Distance to closest coast	Ding et al. (2022a); Onink et al. (2021); Pan et al. (2022); Pedrotti et al. (2016)
Distance to closest largest river	Critchell et al. (2015); Frère et al. (2017); Liu et al. (2022)
Distance to closest largest city	Cózar et al. (2017); Jorquera et al. (2022)
Latitude	Kanhai et al. (2017); Pan et al. (2022); Pogojeva et al. (2021)
Longitude	Kanhai et al. (2017); Pogojeva et al. (2021)
Sea surface salinity	Cózar et al. (2017); Fabri-Ruiz et al. (2023); Kanhai et al. (2017); Lima et al. (2021); Migwi et al. (2020); Pogojeva et al. (2021)
Sea surface temperature	Fabri-Ruiz et al. (2023); Kanhai et al. (2017); Lima et al. (2021); Migwi et al. (2020); Sambolino et al. (2022)
Nitrate	Ding et al. (2022b); Fabri-Ruiz et al. (2023); Liu et al. (2022); Migwi et al. (2020)
Phosphate	Ding et al. (2022b); Fabri-Ruiz et al. (2023); Liu et al. (2022); Migwi et al. (2020)
Dissolved oxygen concentrations	Fabri-Ruiz et al. (2023); Migwi et al. (2020); Pogojeva et al. (2021)
Mixed layer depth	Cózar et al. (2017); Kanhai et al. (2017); Pogojeva et al. (2021)
Dissolved inorganic carbon	Novotna et al. (2022); Romera-Castillo et al. (2018); Ward et al. (2019)
Sea level anomaly	Brach et al. (2018); De Botton Falcón (2021); Lima et al. (2021)
Geostrophic currents velocity	Fabri-Ruiz et al. (2023); Granado et al. (2019); Jorquera et al. (2022); Jorquera et al. (2022); Lima et al. (2021)
Northward currents velocity	Lima et al. (2021)
Eastward currents velocity	Lima et al. (2021)
Wind divergence	Law et al. (2014); Lima et al. (2021); Onink et al. (2019)
Eddy kinetic energy	Brunner et al. (2015); Fabri-Ruiz et al. (2023); Law et al. (2014); Onink et al. (2019)
Currents relative vorticity	Fabri-Ruiz et al. (2023)
Currents divergence	Fabri-Ruiz et al. (2023)
Currents direction	Jorquera et al. (2022)

Appendix B

Univariate analysis

Figure B.1: Correlation matrix (Spearman's rank correlation ρ) between the final predictors. The cross indicates that $|\rho| > 0.7$

Figure B.2: The non-metric multidimensional scaling plot of the 10 final predictors and coloured by the ocean or sea they belong. The stress is used to terminate the iterative procedure and it is a measure of the quality of the result, which should be close to 0 for perfect solutions (Rabinowitz, 1975)

Figure B.3: The Principal Component Analysis plot of the 10 final predictors and coloured by the ocean or sea they belong. The arrows represent the Eigenvectors of the analysis.

Table B.1: Predictors sets as defined with the hierarchical clustering

Set3.1	dic_surf_osesthz	ugos	oxygen	-	-	-	-
Set3.2	log_phosphate	currents_direction	sst_oisstv2	-	-	-	-
Set3.3	log_nitrate	ugos	log_total_currents	-	-	-	-
Set3.4	sss_cci_smos	currents_direction	wind_u10_era5	-	-	-	-
Set3.5	log_phosphate	ugos	oxygen	-	-	-	-
Set4.1	dic_surf_osesthz	log_phosphate	ugos	oxygen	-	-	-
Set4.2	sss_cci_smos	log_nitrate	currents_direction	sst_oisstv2	-	-	-
Set4.3	dic_surf_osesthz	log_phosphate	ugos	log_total_currents	-	-	-
Set4.4	sss_cci_smos	log_nitrate	currents_direction	wind_u10_era5	-	-	-
Set4.5	dic_surf_osesthz	log_phosphate	ugos	sst_oisstv2	-	-	-
Set5.1	dic_surf_osesthz	log_phosphate	ugos	log_total_currents	oxygen	-	-
Set5.2	sss_cci_smos	log_nitrate	currents_direction	log_total_currents	sst_oisstv2	-	-
Set5.3	dic_surf_osesthz	log_phosphate	ugos	log_total_currents	wind_u10_era5	-	-
Set5.4	sss_cci_smos	log_nitrate	currents_direction	log_total_currents	oxygen	-	-
Set5.5	dic_surf_osesthz	log_phosphate	ugos	log_total_currents	sst_oisstv2	-	-
Set6.1	dic_surf_osesthz	log_nitrate	log_phosphate	ugos	log_total_currents	oxygen	-
Set6.2	sss_cci_smos	log_nitrate	log_phosphate	currents_direction	log_total_currents	sst_oisstv2	-
Set6.3	dic_surf_osesthz	log_nitrate	log_phosphate	ugos	log_total_currents	wind_u10_era5	-
Set6.4	sss_cci_smos	log_nitrate	log_phosphate	currents_direction	log_total_currents	oxygen	-
Set6.5	dic_surf_osesthz	log_nitrate	log_phosphate	ugos	log_total_currents	sst_oisstv2	-
Set7.1	dic_surf_osesthz	log_nitrate	log_phosphate	currents_direction	ugos	log_total_currents	oxygen
Set7.2	sss_cci_smos	log_nitrate	log_phosphate	currents_direction	ugos	log_total_currents	sst_oisstv2
Set7.3	dic_surf_osesthz	log_nitrate	log_phosphate	currents_direction	ugos	log_total_currents	wind_u10_era5
Set7.4	sss_cci_smos	log_nitrate	log_phosphate	currents_direction	ugos	log_total_currents	oxygen
Set7.5	dic_surf_osesthz	log_nitrate	log_phosphate	currents_direction	ugos	log_total_currents	sst_oisstv2

Appendix C

Multivariate analysis

Table C.1: Hyperparameter options for the Random Forest (RF). The values for tuning are the possible hyperparameter values used for the random grid search. We have nevertheless decided to use the default values due to time constraints and because the tuning did not produce considerable differences

Hyperparameter	Tuning values	Selected default values
<i>n_{tree}</i>	30, 130, 230, 330, 430, 530, 630, 730, 830, 930	50
<i>m_{try}</i>	1, 2, 3	-1
<i>min_{rows}</i>	1, 3, 5, 10	1
<i>max_{depth}</i>	10, 20, 30	20
<i>r_{sample}</i>	0.55, 0.632, 0.70, 0.80	0.632

Table C.2: Hyperparameter options for the Gradient Boosting Machine (GBM). The values for tuning are the possible hyperparameter values used for the random grid search. We have nevertheless decided to use the default values due to time constraints and because the tuning did not produce considerable differences

Hyperparameter	Tuning values	Selected default values
<i>max_{depth}</i>	1, 3, 5	5
<i>min_{rows}</i>	1, 5, 10	10
<i>r_{learn}</i>	0.01, 0.05, 0.1	0.1
<i>r_{sample}</i>	0.5, 0.75, 1	1
<i>r_{samplecolumns}</i>	0.8, 0.9, 1	1

Table C.3: Hyperparameter options for the Artificial Neural Network (ANN). The values for tuning are the possible hyperparameter values used for the random grid search. We have nevertheless decided to use the default values due to time constraints and because the tuning did not produce considerable differences

Hyperparameter	Tuning values	Selected default values
activation function	Rectifier, Rectifier with dropout, Tanh, Maxout, Maxout with dropout	Rectifier
hidden layer structure	(5, 5), (10, 10), (15, 15), (20, 20), (50, 50, 50)	(200,200)
λ_{L_1}	0, 1×10^{-3} , 1×10^{-5}	0
λ_{L_2}	0, 1e-3, 1e-5	0

Table C.4: Reference values found in the literature for different ocean basins and seas used for comparison. Conc. are expressed in items/km² (in log10), while Total count (in log10) represents the integrated number of plastic items in the whole area. The results by Eriksen et al. (2014) were obtained from modelling, while all the others from observations.

Basin	Conc.	Total count	Study
Arctic ocean	3	-	Yakushev et al. (2021)
Atlantic ocean	-	12.0	Eriksen et al. (2014)
Bay of Bengal	4.7	-	Sambandam et al. (2022)
Indian ocean	-	11.9	Eriksen et al. (2014)
Mediterranean sea	5.4	11.2	Pedrotti et al. (2022); Eriksen et al. (2014)
Pacific ocean	-	12.4	Eriksen et al. (2014)
Red sea	3.5	-	Martí et al. (2017)
Sea of Japan	6.2	-	Isobe et al. (2015)

Figure C.1: Null model 1 with the associated performance metrics

Figure C.2: Null model 2 with the associated performance metrics

Figure C.3: Surface microplastics concentrations simulated for the year 2015, adapted from the results by Kaandorp et al. (prep) and used for the comparison

Figure C.4: Average annual microplastic concentrations for each set and model.

Figure C.5: Average annual microplastic concentrations for each set and model (black line). The grey ribbon indicates the first and third quartile.

Figure C.6: Average annual microplastic concentrations across the sets for each model (black point). The vertical bars represent the first and third quartile

Figure C.7: Global microplastic concentrations for the chosen set (set6.2), averaged over all months and all models. Values are shown as \log_{10} and expressed as items/km². Black points indicate the regions where the standard deviation between models > 1 , indicating a higher models disagreement and therefore lower prediction confidence.

Figure C.8: Total number of microplastic items for each model for the chosen set (set6.2), averaged over all months and integrated over the grid cell area. Values are shown as \log_{10} and expressed as number of items per grid cell.

Figure C.9: Latitudinal pattern of microplastic concentrations of the chosen set (set6.2) for each model. Latitude is represented on the x-axis.

Figure C.10: Performance metric values grouped by number of predictors and averaged across models and sets

Figure C.11: Boxplot of the normalized standard deviation between models for each set. Low values indicate a higher agreement between the models in the predictions

Figure C.12: Boxplot of the normalized standard deviation between sets for each model. Low values indicate a higher agreement between the predictors sets in the predictions

Figure C.13: Fractional uncertainty (or relative uncertainty) coming from the model choice and the predictors choice at the monthly timescale. Total uncertainty represents the sum of the two fractional uncertainties

Figure C.14: Geographical distribution of models residual for the ensemble mean. Red color indicates a model underestimation, while blue colors a model overestimation

Figure C.15: Models predictions of the ensemble mean against observations. Points closer to the identity line (black line) indicates a smaller error. The blue line represents the linear best fit with the corresponding coefficient of correlation R^2

Figure C.16: Model residuals of the ensemble mean against models predictions. The points should be randomly distributed around the zero line (black line) and the blue line representing the linear best fit with the corresponding coefficient of correlation R^2 should be flat. This indicates that the errors are randomly distributed and independent

Figure C.17: Relative difference in percentage terms between the ensemble mean results for each model and the results by Kaandorp et al. (prep). Purple (red) colour indicates that our models' predictions are higher (lower).

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